

Cognition Perspective on MuDForM

Robert Deckers
robert.deckers@atomfreeit.com

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Abstract

This report serves as dataset and background for the paper “*Engineering a Cognition-based Modeling Method*” from R. Deckers and P. Lago [15].

Context. We envision a software development process in which involved people capture knowledge and decisions in a way that is close to how they communicate and think. Therefore, we are investigating a method, called MuDForM, to formalize and integrate knowledge of multiple domains into domain models and into specifications in terms of those domain models. We have defined and followed an approach for the creation of the method, which has led to the first version.

Goal. Put the method and its development in the perspective of cognition literature, in order to evaluate to what extent the method is cognition-based.

Method. We started reading and listening to literature on linguistics, philosophy, and cognitive science, mainly hinted by domain experts, and we iteratively added referred and citing literature to the reading list. We bookmarked sections that we considered relevant for the method and its development. We wrote a finding for each bookmark, and allocated it to one or more categories related to the method definition and its creation. We analyzed how each finding implicates the method and its creation, and grouped the results in different themes.

Result. We read and listened to about 150 books, of which 29 led to 80 bookmarks with findings. Their analysis led to 69 reflection snippets, which underpin or challenge method definition choices, or suggest considerations or improvements. The snippets are grouped in eight themes that form a cognition-based reflection on each concept in the method definition. We conclude that the reflection breaks ground for making software development cognition-based; software development can benefit from synergy between method engineering and cognitive sciences.

1 Introduction

This report reflects on the MuDForM method definition from a cognition perspective. It serves as dataset and background of the paper “Engineering a Cognition-based Specification Method” [15], from now on called the *the paper*.

Software development is a process of integrating human knowledge and decisions. There is no transportation or transformation of material. All development activities and results are conceptual. In our experience, existing programming and specification languages do not support (most) people in capturing their knowledge and decisions. That is why we started our research to create a method, including a language. We set out to find fundamental concepts from human cognition, with natural language as an entry point. We learned the notion of Mentalese as the language of the mind [43, 41]. But Mentalese is not defined and there is no consensus among linguists and cognitive scientists on what its concepts or grammar are. As expected, the search for cognitive concepts was not that simple.

Meanwhile, we wanted to work on the actual method. So, we first looked into existing domain-oriented methods. We decided to start with a method that is close to natural language: the KISS method [30]. We defined its metamodel, method steps, and viewpoints, because they were not well-documented. From our 30 years of modeling experience, we documented guidelines and let them be reviewed. The KISS method does not provide support for dealing with multiple domains and for using existing methods and languages. We had designed solutions for these topics in industry projects, but never generalized and documented them before. We applied and improved the method through case studies.

1.1 Problem Statement and Contribution

In parallel, we found elementary concepts in the cognition literature that fit the defined method. We call them cognitive aspects (see Section 5 of *the paper*). Along the way, we produced findings for the MuDForM definition that underpin, refute, or just challenge some method design choices, or suggest method improvements or future research. This report reflects on those. The result is far from complete with respect to the wide span of the cognitive literature and raises many potential research questions. However, we believe that we have opened the door to making software development more cognition-based.

This report is not technical. It illustrates how the fields of software development and cognitive science can join forces. The vision of MuDForM is a development method based on human thinking and communication. It should capture human knowledge and decisions, and produce specifications suitable for system development, and software development in particular. It is fine if this is partially achieved by utilizing existing computer-based and mathematical methods, languages, and formalisms. But those are not the starting point.

The report is organized as follows. Section 1.1 describes the problem statement and contribution. Section 2 clarifies the method creation concepts that form the context of this report. Section 3 explains the followed research methodology. Section 4 reflects on the vision, the main research goal, and some of the method objectives, which are (partially) published in [13] and [14]. To make this report self-contained, we have put them in Appendices B, C, and D, respectively. Section 5 reflects on the concepts that make up the MuDForM definition. Sections 4 and 5 are based on reflection snippets from Appendix A. Section 6 discusses the results. Section 8 analyzes the limitations of this study. Section 7 discusses related work. Section 9 concludes this report and lists the main suggestions for future work.

1.1 Problem Statement and Contribution

This section describes the problem that this report addresses and clarifies how it contributes to that problem. The goal of defining a specification method that is based on knowledge from cognitive and related sciences is achieved through three tasks. The first task is to identify useful concepts from cognitive science. To our knowledge, there is no published and agreed upon set of cognitive concepts that can be used to design a (specification) language or method. We need to identify those concepts ourselves. The second task is to determine how identified cognitive concepts can be used in the method definition. The third task is to define the method using the

Chapter 1. Introduction

identified cognitive concepts.

This report contributes to the first and second task. It provides a reflection from a cognitive science perspective on the creation of MuDForM, *i.e.*, it identifies cognitive concepts, it underpins or refutes some of the method design choices, and it suggests topics for further research and improvements for the method. This reflection can be used for future work on MuDForM, or other cognition-based methods. Furthermore, this report shows how knowledge rooted in cognitive science can be used in the creation of a specification method, which can be used by developers of other methods. Section 6 of *the paper* addresses the third task.

This report does not claim to be complete regarding the potential of using cognitive science in software development and method engineering in particular. Rather, it aims to break ground for more direct support for human thinking and communication in (software) development.

2 Method Creation Context

The method definition and development approach for MuDForM form the context for the reflection presented in this report. Although we have tried not to assume detailed knowledge of MuDForM, we cannot avoid the fact that this report refers to some modeling concepts defined in *the paper*. It might be useful to consult or read them to understand this report. The concepts are presented in Figure 2.1. We refer to

Figure 2.1: Method creation ingredients (UML class diagram)

Chapter 2. Method Creation Context

instances of the concepts in the following ways:

- The **Method objectives (O_i)** are represented by their number, given in Appendix D:
 - O1 Distinction of multiple domains.
 - O2 Independence from any domain.
 - O3 Self-contained specifications.
 - O4 Distinction between descriptive specifications and prescriptive specifications.
 - O5 Specification of state and specification of change.
 - O6 Transformation of natural language into models that are close to human cognition.
 - O7 An engineered method that addresses consistency, completeness, traceability, knowledge elicitation, and a comprehensive definition (meta-model, viewpoints, method steps, guidelines)
 - O8 Clear relation between specifications and architecture.
- The names of **Cognitive aspects**, described in Section 5 of *the paper*, are in typescript font, e.g., Concept, Category, Analogy, and Statement context.
- The names of **Modeling concepts**, introduced in Section 6.3 of *the paper*, are in *italics sans-serif font*, e.g., Classifier, Activity, and Function step.

3 Research Method

This report addresses the following research question:

What are common elementary cognitive concepts that people use to think and communicate, and how can they be applied in engineering a specification method?

To answer this question, we followed an approach that can be described as qualitative data analysis. This research method involves examining non-numerical data, such as texts, to uncover patterns and meanings (see for example the book of Huberman *et al.* [27]). The steps typically include collecting data, organizing the data, coding the data, analyzing the data to draw conclusions, and finally reporting the insights.

Figure 3.1: Concepts in the qualitative data analysis (UML class diagram)

Our qualitative data analysis is managed through the concepts depicted in Figure 3.1. It consists of the following steps:

Chapter 3. Research Method

- **Data collection:** We searched for literature in the field of philosophy, linguistics, and cognitive sciences, for which the studies from our SLR [13] that addressed the use of natural language, were used as a starting point.

A general search on language philosophy and cognitive science, and talks with linguists, led us to books of Noam Chomsky [8], Steven Pinker [41], John McWhorter [38], and John Searle [48].

After that, we followed a snowballing approach (as described by Jalali and Wohlin [28]), by iteratively identifying and reading publications, mostly books, of authors that were mentioned in the already included literature. We also read some general books about design and architecture [39, 21].

It resulted in reading and listening to about 150 books and recorded university lectures in the period April 2015 to December 2023. 29 of those *publications*¹ yielded about 80 *bookmarks* that we considered to be relevant for the creation of MuDForM. We have created a document titled Cognition Literature Analysis [12], in which we recorded our observations, considerations, and conclusions for each bookmark, from now on called *findings*. When we were unable to define a sensible finding, we discarded the bookmark.

- **Data organization:** We put each bookmark and its finding in a separate *reflection snippet*, from now on simply called *reflection*. We defined categories based on the method creation ingredients presented in Figure 2.1.
- **Coding:** We allocated each reflection to one or more categories.
- **Analysis:** We analyzed how each reflection fits its categories, and defined the *implications* for the corresponding *method creation ingredient*. This led to about 75 *reflections*, each consisting of one or more *bookmarks*, a *finding*, and an *implication*. When we concluded that multiple reflections had approximately the same implications, we combined them in one reflection, leading to 69 final reflections.
- **Reporting:** When we wanted to report on the results, we discovered that the grouping per category did not lead to a set of clear insights and sensible story lines. So, we regrouped all the reflections in a bottom up process to come to eight *reflection themes*. Then, we wrote a conclusion and suggestions for each theme. Every conclusion begins by enumerating the reflections used from Appendix A. Because cognition-based method engineering is a new field, we have chosen to spend relatively much text on future work.

¹ *Italic words* in this section refer to elements from Figure 3.1.

4 Reflection on the Research Background

This section reflects on the vision, research goal, and method objectives presented in Appendices B, C, and D. We first discuss the use of domain-oriented models to convey knowledge. Then, we introduce the notion of basing modeling concepts on cognitive concepts, with natural language as a starting point.

4.1 Use Domain-oriented Models to Convey Knowledge

Used reflections:

A.1.1: 'Use unambiguous models to convey knowledge'

A.1.2: 'People care about their domain. Computers do not know what they are doing'

A.1.3: 'Specifications must mean something to people'

A.1.4: 'Method steps and viewpoints focus the modeling process'

A.1.5: 'Modeling is not an extra activity'

A.1.6: 'Focus on domain-oriented methods'

Books of Pinker [41, 43] and Dennet [17] discuss the computational theory of Alan Turing. Computers do not know what the relation is between their actions and the world outside the computer. For a computer, software is nothing more than a set of instructions; computers just process specifications. To do so, those specifications must be unambiguously interpretable, which requires an unambiguous language. The computer does not require specifications to contain meaningful terms. Meaningful terms are only relevant for people, as addressed by Harari [23], because it enables

Chapter 4. Reflection on the Research Background

them to relate specifications to their knowledge and decisions.

Specifications can be about many areas of knowledge, *i.e.*, domains, of a development activity and its context, and may cover many aspects. A modeler should be supported to focus on one or a few domains and aspects at a time. A method that guides a stepwise modeling process, and provides multiple distinct viewpoints, can provide such support.

The reflections mentioned above underpin our choice to investigate a domain-oriented method to define meaningful, unambiguous specifications.

4.2 Meaningful Cognition-based Models

Natural language has evolved for thousands of years to allow people to communicate about their world. People also have an internal language for thought, *i.e.*, Mentalese, which differs from natural language. Thought existed before language; thought evolved for action.

Used reflections:

A.1.7: 'Exploit the lexical hypothesis'

A.1.8: 'Language awareness is innate'

A.1.9: 'Cognition is more than language'

A.1.10: 'Modeling concepts should be based on Mentalese'

A.1.11: 'Focus on mental concepts; not on the brain or reality'

A.1.12: 'On the evolution of thought'

Levitin [35] discusses the lexical hypothesis, *i.e.*, the most important things humans need to talk about eventually become encoded in language. Language awareness is predominant in humans. Sigman [52] even concludes that it is innate; even babies are language aware. However, thinking is more than using language.

Pinker [44, 41] rejects genuine linguistic determinism, *i.e.*, a person's language determines what the person can think. He states that this is clearly wrong. If it was right, then we could use a metamodel of natural language as the metamodel of MuDForM. But people can and do think without having words or a language-based grammar. They have an internal language for their thoughts, which Pinker calls Mentalese [43]. The MuDForM metamodel should be based on Mentalese, but Mentalese grammar is not explained. The observation that thoughts are inherently unambiguous matches the requirement that software (specifications) must be unambiguous. Natural lan-

4.2 Meaningful Cognition-based Models

guage complicates the direct translation of thoughts into unambiguous specifications. The challenge is to exploit the power and maturity of natural language, while overcoming its ambiguity and indirectness that results from the discrepancy between speech and thought.

As explained by Marian [36], to find the concepts used in thinking, it is not useful to model physical processes and elements in the brain or to try to find exact categories of things in the real world. Finding modeling concepts is not a matter of investigating how the brain or reality works, *i.e.*, it is not about neuroscience or physics. Consequently, the method should support modeling how people perceive, think, and communicate about the world, which underpins the research goal.

Sloman and Fernbach [53] point out that thought existed before language; some animals clearly have thought without language. They mention different reasons why thought evolved: to create a mental model of how the world is, to enable language, to solve problems, or for specific purposes like making tools or finding a mate. These reasons have one thing in common: thought evolved for action. MuDForM can be aligned with natural language, but should not be hindered by it. MuDForM must enable specifying how the world is and what actions occur in it. The specifications of actions must be connectable to the specifications of conditions and consequences.

Furthermore, the reasoning about problems, solutions, and their relations, should be supported. The current definition of MuDForM only enables the specification of problems, solutions, and their relations. It does not explicitly support the reasoning process for solving a problem. To support the reasoning process itself, method steps and guidelines must be defined, and maybe some new modeling concepts. Its investigation is future work.

5 Reflection on the Method Definition

The section reflects on the method definition. It is organized around seven themes that we identified in the reflection snippets of Appendix A.

5.1 Separation of Syntax and Semantics in Mind and Method

Section 5 of *the paper* introduces the cognitive aspects model as a basis for defining modeling concepts. The root of the model is `Concept`. All other cognitive aspects, except `Symbol`, are derived from it. `Concepts` represent units of meaning. `Symbols` represent units of syntax. It appears that this separation between meaning and syntax comes naturally to the mind. But syntax, and choice of words in particular, play an important role in understanding specifications.

Used reflections:

- A.2.1: 'Concepts have meaning'
- A.2.2: 'There are no colorless green ideas that sleep furiously'
- A.2.3: 'Meaningless symbols refer to meaningful concepts'
- A.2.4: 'The mind has representations of concepts too'
- A.2.5: 'A concept can have multiple representations'
- A.2.6: 'Eliminate homonyms and synonyms, but not always'
- A.2.7: 'Involved experts decide about model element names, not the modeler'
- A.2.8: 'Resembling word forms in models'

5.2 Supporting Analysis, Design, and their Context

John Searle [49] discusses the notion of concept according to the philosopher Gottlob Frege: a concept is a function with a truth value, *i.e.*, it is true or false. To determine its truth value, a concept must have meaning, which is covered by the root of the cognitive aspects model, *i.e.*, the class `Concept`. If a MuDForM model is specified correctly, *i.e.*, it complies with the metamodel and model criteria, then it always has a defined meaning. This is significantly different from natural language, where grammatically correct sentences can be meaningless.

The meaning of a model (fragment) is not determined by its syntax, but by the used modeling concepts. Used names and other symbols do not add meaning to a model. The involved (domain) experts must recognize, and preferably choose, the names of model elements, because they must accept, and preferably adopt, the model. To reduce ambiguity, there are steps and guidelines to eliminate homonyms and synonyms, and to standardize logical constructs. The reduction of ambiguity could go further, which requires more research, and is a suggestion for future work.

The use of different word forms, *i.e.*, morphology, helps to understand what kind of word a word is. English uses word endings *e.g.*, -ness, -ability, -ism, and conjugations of verbs. Morphology helps writers choose words and readers understand them. As MuDForM does not prescribe a syntax, model users cannot benefit from this feature. It is future work to investigate whether there are relations between modeling concepts, which can be exploited syntactically to increase model usability. For example, to understand that the class 'Order' is the objectification of the activity 'to Order', or that the function 'Ordering' centers around the execution of 'to Order', or that the state 'Ordered' means that an instance of 'to Order' is executed.

5.2 Supporting Analysis, Design, and their Context

A development team must understand and decide on many aspects of a system and its environment. A specification method must support capturing knowledge about a target domain, decisions about to-be-developed systems, and assumptions about other knowledge and decisions. Section 6.2 of *the paper* explains how these concepts are related. *Context models* serve as an explicit border between a software development team and their environment. Some principles of lexicography are applicable in the definition of MuDForM.

Used reflections:

A.3.1: 'Support analysis and design for multiple domains'

Chapter 5. Reflection on the Method Definition

A.3.2: 'Analysis and design reflect lexical defining and real defining'

A.3.3: 'Domain models give meaning to other specifications'

A.3.7: 'Formal propositions vs. propositions about something'

A.3.4: 'Context models form a foundation for contracts with other parties'

A.3.5: 'Context models support subjectivity'

A.3.6: 'Separate what must happen from what makes it happen'

There is no restriction to what kinds of domains are involved in software development. Software development involves many people, who have their own distinct knowledge, expertise, and goals. MuDForM supports capturing knowledge and decisions from different people, about multiple domains, and supports integrating them by using model elements from one domain in the definition of model elements in another domain. This contributes to the support for multiple domains, for any domain, and for architecture, as expressed in method objectives O1, O2, and O8 respectively.

Stamper [54] discusses lexical defining vs. real defining. Lexical defining is the attempt to describe how a word is used and what it means in a particular setting. Real defining is the attempt to declare the nature of something via defining it. Modeling a *Domain* is describing what can happen and what can exist. It can be seen as an analysis activity and is comparable to lexical defining. Modeling a *Feature* is prescribing what must happen and what must exist. It can be seen as a design activity, and is comparable to real defining. The distinction between the two is expressed in method objective O4. Furthermore, *Feature* models are fully expressed in terms of *Domain models*; *Domain models* are the dictionary for *Feature models*. As a consequence, the meaning of a *Feature model* is always clear.

An example: the domain model defines that you can pour beer from a bottle into a glass, and that the amount of beer that goes out of the bottle equals the amount that goes into the glass. This allows you to specify in a feature model how much beer you should pour and how fast. The context model defines what liquid amounts are. If you also want to express requirements about the amount of beer that may be spilled during pouring, then you made the wrong domain model. In the words of Searle [49], the meaning of the concept was there, but you did not have the language to express it. By capturing concepts in a model, you have the language to use their meaning.

Domain models are intended to describe something that exists. As such, they can be wrong, *i.e.*, they can be inconsistent with the world they describe. This is different for *Feature models*, because they prescribe what should be true in the world. A system can be an incorrect implementation of a *Feature model*, and as a result, the model is an incorrect description of what really happens. But in that case, we do not say that

5.3 Model Engineering through Method Engineering

the *Feature model* is wrong; we say that the implementation is wrong.

Context modeling is neither analysis nor design. Context modeling is just declaring terms. *Context model elements* have a black box definition, *i.e.*, only their externally observable properties are specified, *e.g.*, *signatures*, *invariants*, *preconditions*, and *postconditions*, but their implementation is not. A *Context model* can serve as the foundation for a contract between the architect (and their organization) and the party that provides the implementation of the *Context model elements*.

Formalisms, like logic and mathematics, can be embedded in *Context models* via the Formalisms pattern (see Section 6.1 of *the paper*). This means that one can use the declared formalisms in models. The metamodel of the MuDForM definition is itself also a formalism. For example, if you analyze a *Step* in an *Object lifecycle*, you always know it refers to an *Activity role* of a defined *Domain activity*. This is not caused by the decisions of the modeler; the metamodel enforces it.

Context models can also be used to capture subjectivity. For example, if you have a criterion that you only want to buy ‘beautiful’ books, then you define a Boolean *Operation* that determines if a book is beautiful. You can declare an *Actor* that has the capability to execute that *Operation*. This may lead to the situation where the experienced meaning of the model is non-deterministic, because what books are bought depends on what the assigned *Actor* finds beautiful. However, the model itself is unambiguous.

An explicit step in the MuDForM modeling process is the transition from specifying what must happen in a function execution, to specifying what makes it happen, *i.e.*, assigning *Actors* to *Function steps*. The *Actors* are declared in a *Context model*. Their capabilities, specified in their *Behavior composition*, must match with all the *Function steps* they are assigned to. There is currently a gap in the metamodel concerning the allocation of *Actors* to *Function steps*. Solving this gap is future work.

5.3 Model Engineering through Method Engineering

The methodical engineering of models, as opposed to ad hoc modeling or modeling through experience, is enabled by the maturity of the method ingredients. This section reflects on the application of lexicographical principles, deductively choosing model elements of the right granularity, and how guiding and tracing knowledge elicitation enhance model validity.

5.3.1 Apply Principles for Defining Words

There are different ways to define and learn words that can also be applied in defining model elements.

Used reflections:

A.4.1: 'Support different types of defining a term'

A.4.2: 'Support extensional and intensional defining'

A.4.3: 'Support principles of vocabulary learning'

Stamper [54], Hofstadter and Sander [26], and Flanigan [19] mention different ways of defining words. We analyzed their applicability to our method. We conclude that analytical defining (aka intensional defining) is the main definition form for model elements. This way of defining consists of giving a model element a type, and relating it to other model elements, similar to analytical defining in dictionaries.

A MuDForM model is normalized, *i.e.*, it does not contain redundant model elements. Sometimes experts use a term that does not correspond to a normalized model element, but that is meaningful to them. Such a term must be allowed to increase model acceptance. This can be implemented via derived model elements, which are completely defined in terms of other model elements. For example, let 'car' be a normalized class with an attribute 'number-of-wheels', and suppose experts want to use the term 'tricycle'. By defining that 'tricycle' is a 'car' with 'number-of-wheels' equal to 'three', such 'tricycle' can be used without violating the normalization rules. Extending the metamodel to support derived elements is future work.

All *Named elements* can have a list of *aliases*, which supports synonymous defining. Although real synonyms are scarce in a real-life language, in a system development context, people from different organizational units might use different terms for the same thing. They might also consider different properties of the same thing. In that case, the different terms are not exact synonyms, but it must be possible to state that their instances have the same identity. It should be possible to state that two model elements are the same, *i.e.*, to merge two model elements. Investigating how to realize this in MuDForM is future work.

As discussed in Section 5.1, MuDForM does not support morphology, but it could definitely help in learning; in making models, as well as in understanding models.

5.3.2 Deductive Modeling

The combination of metamodel, method steps and viewpoints, and guidelines help to deductively decide about what becomes a model element and what not.

Used reflections:

A.4.4: 'Avoid different ways of modeling the same meaning'

A.4.5: 'There should be guidelines for determining the right granularity of model elements'

A.4.6: 'Guidelines for deciding which concepts become a model element'

A.4.7: 'Guidelines for distinguishing model elements'

The MuDForM guidelines and criteria assure that models are normalized, *i.e.*, they do not have redundancies. For example, for defining family roles you only need the concepts of person, being a parent, and gender. You can specify the concepts father, mother, sibling, grandparent, cousin, etc., by expressing them in terms of parent relations and gender.

Furthermore, there are guidelines to prevent that knowledge can be modeled in different ways. They are gathered in Reflection A.4.7: 'Guidelines for distinguishing model elements' and their description can be found in the full method definition [11]. It is unclear how many of the possible choices for each method step can be directed by the current set of guidelines. We suspect there can be more, *e.g.*, for distinguishing *Attributes*. Finding out requires more investigation and is future work.

5.3.3 Guiding and Tracing Knowledge Elicitation Enhance Model Validity

Models represent situation-independent knowledge, which might be elicited directly from experts or other sources, or derived from situation specific information. Explicit method steps and viewpoints help to ease the traceability of analysis and modeling decisions, which enhances the validity of models.

Used reflections:

A.4.8: 'Models represent situation-independent knowledge'

A.4.9: 'Support knowledge elicitation from both semantic memory and episodic memory'

A.4.10: 'Traceability helps to prevent falsities'

A.4.11: 'Traceability and multiple viewpoints help to detect biases'

Chapter 5. Reflection on the Method Definition

Goleman [22] discusses that people can have situation-independent thought. They can think and talk about situations they are not in right now, or they can generalize knowledge from the situation they are in. Pinker [43] states that compositional thoughts are often about individuals. The thought that a particular person eats an apple is different from the thought that people eat apples in general. People are capable of thinking things like ‘there is an X that Y’ without knowing such X, or things like ‘for all Xs: Y’ without knowing all Xs. Corballis [9] writes about the notions of episodic memory and semantic memory. Episodic memory is memory for events or episodes in our lives. For example, remembering that you ate an apple this morning. Semantic memory is memory for statements about the world. For example, remembering that Amsterdam is the capital of the Netherlands, or that people can eat apples.

Experts can be asked to share general knowledge about the targeted domain or system (from their semantic memory). They can make statements that are generic, as in ‘People can order a book’. This type of statement can be used directly as model input.

Experts can also be asked about events that happen(ed) in their domain (from their episodic memory). They can make instance-specific statements, as in ‘John ordered Lord of the Rings’. Such a statement needs to be generalized to become model input, *i.e.*, by asking what kind of thing ‘John’ is, what kind of thing ‘Lord of the Rings’ is, what kind of thing ‘orders’ is, and what other things can ‘order’ or be ‘ordered’. The guideline ‘Ask for examples when generic knowledge is hard to phrase’ appeals to the episodic memory of the involved expert.

A model can be seen as a representation of semantic memory. When a model is executed, it creates events, which can be logged and form a representation of episodic memory.

The knowledge that experts share, can be false and incomplete. It does not necessarily mean they are lying. They might simply be biased, or do not possess the right knowledge. All decisions during grammatical analysis and modeling can be logged in terms of the involved model elements, taken steps, and applied guidelines. This means that any inconsistency in the resulting model can be traced back to the input. The model viewpoints are defined on one metamodel, which also supports the detection of inconsistencies across views. Traceability, in accordance with method objective O7, reduces the chance that a model contains falsities.

Of course, it is still possible that falsities end up in the model. A bias in an input text that is transformed into a model, is probably also present in that model; bias

in, bias out. Letting other experts validate a model, either directly via a review, or indirectly via a translation into natural language or another representation, prevents that a model is based on the biases of one person. It is future work to investigate if it is possible to find analysis and modeling guidelines that explicitly target a specific type of bias.

5.4 Match Reality with Useful Categories

Modeled categories must be consistent with the real-world concepts (objects) that they describe. Useful categories are not determined by observable properties of objects, but through the actions that their objects undergo, *i.e.*, useful categories are functional categories. Objects can belong to multiple categories throughout their existence. Whether multiple objects in the real world might correspond to one instance of a model element depends on their distinguishability. Changes in the real world may impact instances of a model, and sometimes also the model itself.

Used reflections:

A.5.1: 'Categories enable inference of properties'

A.5.2: 'Prevent mismatches between reality and model'

A.5.3: 'Classifiers must represent functional categories'

A.5.4: 'Support multiple functional categories for one instance'

A.5.5: 'A model is a complete specification of the world it describes'

A.5.6: 'It must be unambiguously determinable if an object belongs to a category'

A.5.7: 'Different objects in the real world can correspond to one model instance'

A.5.8: 'Objects differ if and only if they are distinguishable'

A.5.9: 'Objects are not tied to one category'

A.5.10: 'There are no exact category definitions in the real world'

In "How the mind works" [43], Steven Pinker concludes that 'the mind has to get something out of forming categories'. That something is inference. Obviously, we can not know everything about every object. But we can observe some of its properties, assign it to a category, and from the category predict properties that we did not observe. 'If Mopsy has long ears, he is a rabbit; if he is a rabbit, he should eat carrots, go hippity-hop, and breed like, well, a rabbit.'

The cognitive aspect *Category* represents the notion of category as meant by Pinker. *Category* is a subclass of *Concept*. It is implemented via the modeling concept *Classifier*, which can have *Generalization* relations to other *Classifiers*. *Classifiers* can

Chapter 5. Reflection on the Method Definition

have instances, *i.e.*, objects, and actions. If you know an instance of a *Classifier*, then it must have values for the specified properties of that *Classifier*. If it does not, then either the *Classifier's* definition is incorrect, the classification is incorrect, or your knowledge about the instance is incorrect. Correct the model or the instance such that the consistency between them is ensured. This reasoning is captured in the modeling guideline *Ensure consistency between classifiers and known instances*.

Levitin [35] and Pinker [41] discuss the notion and importance of categorizing: perceptual and conceptual. We categorize things because they look, sound, smell alike. But also because they can fulfill some function in some context. The latter categories are called functional categories. MuDForM follows the notion of functional categories. Objects do not belong to the same category because they look (or sound, or smell) the same, but because you do the same things with them. Vice versa, objects belong to a different category when you do something different with them, *i.e.*, they undergo different types of actions. MuDForM has several guidelines driven by the notion of functional categorizing, which help to identify the right categories and their properties (see Reflection A.4.7: 'Guidelines for distinguishing model elements').

It is impossible to specify a concept in the real world completely. This is not the case for concepts that are an instance of a model. A model of a concept can be seen as a complete specification of that concept. For example, if a car is defined as a thing with wheels, then a bicycle and a shopping cart are also cars. This is correct if only the wheel-having property is important. If you want to know how many passengers it can transport, it is clearly an incomplete definition.

Searle [49] and Pinker [44] point to the difference between being countable and having identity. Two objects are identical if and only if they have the same properties. MuDForM follows this rule, called Leibniz's law. This means that two real-world objects without distinguishing properties correspond to one model instance. For example, two plastic cups that look exactly the same may correspond to one model instance that has the properties of that type of plastic cup. To distinguish the two cups requires them to have distinctive properties.

Several authors (Spinoza [34], Pinker [42], Hofstadter and Sander [26], Lakoff [32]) state that there is no precisely defined category for each object in the real world, as was presumed by classical philosophers. Categorizations of objects change, because both object properties and category properties can change. MuDForM currently covers the former situation. Objects belong to *Classes*, which can have *Generalization* relations. Objects may switch *Classes* throughout their life, as long as the those *Classes* are related via a *Generalization* relation.

The change of category definitions is covered partially. All instances have a model element as type, and all model elements are *Classifier*. But MuDForM does currently not have explicit operations for allocating an instance to a different model element or to change a model element. Those operations can be determined when the meta-model is extended with modeling activities, like ‘to *Objectify an Activity into a Class*’, or ‘to *Retype an Attribute with a Class*’. Currently, only the metamodel part for grammatical analysis contains activities (see the full method description [11]). Extending the metamodel with activities to deal with model changes is future work.

5.5 Time is Perceived through Events

Time is not an innate mental concept. Time is perceived through events. Events are ordered relative to each other. The method supports different options for ordering events.

Used reflections:

A.6.1: ‘Events are ordered in time, and have a duration’

A.6.2: ‘The past is determined by the events that have happened’

A.6.3: ‘Lifecycles enable stepping through time’

Pinker [44] observes that time is encoded in grammar in two ways. First, in tense, *i.e.*, past, present, and future. The other is called aspect, which is about the shape of the event. For example, instantaneous, as in ‘swat a fly’, open-ended, as in ‘running around’, a marking of completion, as in ‘draw a circle’. A third one is called reference time, *i.e.*, an event to which is referred. For example, ‘I ate before I showered’, in which, ‘I showered’ is the reference time.

The cognitive aspects model has an order relation between Events. The changes relation between Action and Object has a timing aspect, because one can speak of the object state before and after an action. Regarding the event shape, a modeled *Activity* can be *atomic* or *non-atomic*. Actions that are an instance of an *atomic Activity* have by definition a timestamp. Instances of a *non-atomic Activity* always have a starting time, and if they are finished, they also have a stopping time.

Object lifecycles and *Function lifecycles*, allow, as a matter of speaking, to virtually travel through time. An object and a function execution are always at some point in their *lifecycle*. One can speak of the actions that happened before, the actions that happen now, and the actions that can or must happen. The Flow structure pattern,

Chapter 5. Reflection on the Method Definition

which is the foundation for *lifecycles* offers several possibilities to order *Steps*, e.g., sequential or parallel, and optional or obligatory. A *lifecycle*, combined with a log of all actions that happened in the life of an object, enable reasoning about the next actions of that object.

5.6 Building Modeling Concepts from Natural Language

We discuss some common language constructs and generic word categories that we found in literature, and how they are used in the definition of MuDForM. We conclude that more natural language concepts can be used as the foundation of modeling concepts or in the transition from text to model.

Used reflections:

- A.7.1: 'Language is common, but there is no common language'
- A.7.2: 'Support for words that are common in all languages'
- A.7.3: 'Support part of speech concepts'
- A.7.4: 'Support modeling verbs, and their temporal contour'
- A.7.5: 'Support to be, to have, to do, and to go'
- A.7.6: 'Support different meanings of to be'
- A.7.8: 'Support different types of speech acts'
- A.7.7: 'Support specification of location, force, agency, and causation'
- A.7.9: 'Support Subject-Verb-Object sentences'
- A.7.10: 'Compound names correlate with hierarchy between concepts'
- A.7.11: 'Attributes and steps support indexicals'
- A.7.12: 'Support word definitions and word usage'

Section 4 mentioned that language is common, and language awareness is innate. But according to Searle [48], linguists do not agree on universal language rules. To define modeling concepts, we searched concepts that are common in most languages. The search results can be divided in word categories, and language constructs.

Pinker [43] lists word categories that are common in all languages. The MuDForM support differs per category. For example, logical connectives, e.g., 'not', 'and', and 'same', are directly supported, but motion and space are not.

We analyzed how the main parts of speech of the English language, *i.e.*, noun, pronoun, adjective, determiner, verb, adverb, preposition, conjunction, and interjection, are covered by MuDForM (see Reflection A.7.3: 'Support part of speech concepts').

5.6 Building Modeling Concepts from Natural Language

All relevant parts are currently addressed in the *Grammatical analysis* step. There are guidelines for choosing the right conversion, but we think that the *Text-to-model transformation* step can be extended with more guidelines.

We specifically analyzed the modeling of verbs, as hinted by Hofstadter and Sander [26], and in accordance with method objective O5. We analyzed how different types of verbs, and the common verbs to be (in different meanings), to do, to have, and to go, are supported (see Sections A.7.4, A.7.5, and A.7.6). We conclude that the different verbs and meanings are supported directly by modeling concepts, except for verbs relating to location and motion. We think that these should also be supported directly by modeling concepts, and we suggest how in Section A.7.7. The corresponding method definition part and its validation are future work.

In the lectures on “Philosophy of Language” [49], John Searle discusses different types of speech acts (assertive, directive, commissive, expressive, and declaration). We have analyzed the modeling possibilities for the different types of speech acts and conclude that all, except expressive, are addressed in some way. It is unclear whether they are covered correctly. More investigation is needed for the support of different types of speech acts with modeling concepts and guidelines. This is a suggestion for future work.

With respect to language constructs, we analyzed the support for the Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) structure of sentences, for compound names, and for indexicals¹. Each of them is explicitly supported by modeling concepts and guidelines.

Dennet [17] discusses the notion of words and tokens of a word, *i.e.*, the word and its meaning, and the use of the word in sentences. The word ‘word’ has four tokens in the previous sentence, and two in this one. This notion is present in many places in the metamodel, *e.g.*, the type of an *Attribute*, is a token of the *Class* that it refers to, and a *Function step* in a *Function lifecycle* refers to an *Activity*, hence, the *Function step* is a token of that *Activity*. The *Structure* pattern and its derivatives manifest the notion. In general, a *Reference* in a *Structure* is a token of the *Referred item* (see Section 6.1 of *the paper*).

¹An indexical refers to something in its context, *e.g.*, “I”, “here”, and “now”.

5.7 More Cognitive Aspects and Derived Modeling Concepts

Besides the cognitive aspects and corresponding modeling concepts that are discussed in the previous section, we identified some cognitive concepts that are not directly based on language constructs: the three principles of connections between ideas from David Hume, the generic concept of hierarchy between concepts, the mental concept of analogy making, and the difference between performative and constative speech acts.

Used reflection:

A.8.1: ‘Support possible connections between ideas’

Steven Pinker [45] refers to the 1748 book on human understanding of philosopher David Hume: ‘There appear to be only three principles of connections between ideas: similarity, contiguity in time or place, and cause or effect.’ Those connections are expressed as relations between sentences or partial sentences.

- Regarding Similarity: the cognitive aspect *AnaLoGy* reflects the specification of similarity. Stating that something belongs to a *Category* is also an expression of similarity. What it means to state that two model fragments are similar, is not obvious. However, it could be useful to model, *e.g.*, to analyze if properties of one model element also hold for another model element. For example, you can say that a car is similar to a horse. You can carry stuff with a horse. Can you also carry stuff with a car?
- Regarding Contiguity: the cognitive aspect *Event* has an order with itself. *Function lifecycles* and *Object lifecycles*, which are based on the *Flow structure* pattern, are used to specify contiguity in time. Contiguity of place is not supported at the moment, It is future work, as suggested in Section 5.6.
- Regarding Cause effect: an *Event* can cause another *Event*. An *Agent* may perform an *Event*, which is a kind of causation too. *Function lifecycles* specify what should happen when. Via the *behavior modality* of *Function steps*, the observation and generation of events can be specified, *i.e.*, what event causes a *Function step* to execute, and what event is generated by a *Function step*. The effect of a *Function step* is defined by the *Activity* it refers to.

Used reflections:

5.7 More Cognitive Aspects and Derived Modeling Concepts

A.8.2: ‘Support the specification of hierarchy between concepts’

A.8.3: ‘Support making abstractions’

Hofstadter and Sander [26] observe that concepts are hierarchical. We are building concepts from other concepts throughout our whole life. The cognitive aspect Property reflects hierarchy. The main mechanism in the metamodel for capturing hierarchy is the Structure pattern and its derivatives (see Section 6.1 of *the paper*). It is applied to most relation types in the metamodel, such as *Behavior composition*, *Generalization*, *Attribute*, and *Object lifecycle*.

One form of hierarchy, that Hofstadter and Sander discuss, is making abstractions. ‘People are constantly abstracting. This is not stupidity, but intelligence.’ To make abstractions, MuDForM offers the concept of *Generalizations* between *Classifiers*. Furthermore, the modeling concept *Classifier* is itself an abstraction mechanism; a *Classifier* is an abstraction of a set of instances. For example, the *classifier* Apple can be seen as an abstraction of one or more specific apples. Generally speaking, making models is making abstractions.

Used reflections:

A.8.4: ‘Support the specification of analogies’

A.8.5: ‘Any model fragment can be seen as a pattern’

Hofstadter and Sander [26] dedicated a whole book to analogies being at the core of mental processes. AnaLoGy is identified as one of the cognitive aspects, but MuDForM does not support it yet with specific modeling concepts. Of course, you can select a model fragment, copy it, rename the elements, and paste it in the target model, which reflects making an analogy. We think that guided analogy making would be a useful extension to MuDForM. How to support it properly requires more investigation and is future work.

Used reflection:

A.8.6: ‘Distinguish performative from constative speech acts’

Searle [49] elaborates on the difference between performative speech acts and constative speech acts. A performative speech act is performing an action by saying something, *e.g.*, ‘waiter, get me a beer please’ is the act of ordering a beer. A constative speech act would be ‘the waiter is getting me a beer’.

A software system can perform an action if it is a performative speech act, *e.g.*, order a beer via an app on your phone, which sends the order to a back-end system.

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Constative speech acts can only be controlled by a software system via a call to some actor (operator or actuator) to perform the action, *e.g.*, the back-end system tells the waiter (or a robot) to deliver a beer. Constative speech acts can also be observed by a software system via an interface on which an actor (user or sensor) indicates that an action happened, *e.g.*, the waiter confirms the delivery of a beer.

Modeling concepts to distinguish conceptual and physical activities could be useful. Investigating the support and benefits of different types of speech acts –there are more types, *e.g.*, see Section 5.6– is future work.

6 Discussion

This section discusses the reflections from Appendix A and their summaries in Sections 4 and 5. We first discuss the reflection on the method creation ingredients, and then the different types of reflections.

6.1 Cognition-based Method Definition

Section 4 and Appendix A.1 discuss how the studied literature relates to our vision, research goal, and method objectives (described in Appendices B, C, and D). The primary insight is that the need for unambiguity in software languages coincides with the inherent unambiguity of human thought. Building a metamodel from thought-based concepts does not raise a contradiction. Of course, those concepts must still be identified.

Seven of the eight method objectives are involved at least once in one of the reflections from Appendix A. This does not prove that the method objectives are correct or complete. It demonstrates that cognition and linguistics literature can be related to them, and that maybe more literature can be studied to fine-tune the method objectives. Objective O8, *i.e.*, the support for architecture, is an exception, because we only reflected on it through bookmarks in design and architecture literature.

Section 4 of *the paper* introduces the ingredients that make up the definition of MuDForM. We found content related to each of the method ingredients in Figure 2.1. We made reflections that implied modeling concepts, method steps, and guidelines.

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We found content related to viewpoints in general, but not to specific viewpoints. We also identified potential method ingredients that are not yet covered by MuDForM. Their addition is future work.

Section 5 of *the paper* introduces the cognitive aspects in the diagrams of Figures 2 and 3. We made reflections for each of the elements in Figure 2. We conclude that it makes sense to let all cognitive aspects, except `Symbol`, be a subclass of `Concept`. The reflections also discussed which modeling concepts were based on each cognitive aspect.

The cognitive aspects `Statement` and `Statement context` in Figure 3 in *the paper* are not mentioned in any reflection. Linguists and philosophers use other terms, such as *speech act*, *concept*, *symbol*, *idea*, *sentence*, *word*, and *phrase*. We think that `Statement` resembles the term ‘speech act’ from Searle [49]. We suggest studying speech act theory, to determine if the concepts around the cognitive aspect `Statement` should be changed or extended.

Section 6.1 of *the paper* explains the construction patterns that we used in the definition of the MuDForM metamodel. Each of the three patterns occurred in at least one reflection. The Named Elements pattern is addressed in Section 5.1. The Structure pattern is mentioned at several places, mostly in Section 5.7. The Formalisms pattern is mentioned in Section 5.2. This does not mean that the patterns are optimal or complete. Rather, it shows that they correlate with cognitive or linguistic concepts.

6.2 Different Types of Reflections

During the analysis of the *bookmarks*, we discovered four different types of *findings* and *implications*:

- Some underpin a method design choice, A.7.11: ‘Attributes and steps support indexicals’ or A.7.3: ‘Support part of speech concepts’.
- Some challenge a method design choice, *e.g.*, A.5.10: ‘There are no exact category definitions in the real world’.
- Some suggest an improvement for the method, *e.g.*, A.8.6: ‘Distinguish performative from constative speech acts’.
- Some bookmarks just inspired a finding that made us consider a cognitive concept, *e.g.*, A.4.11: ‘Traceability and multiple viewpoints help to detect biases’.

6.2 Different Types of Reflections

and A.3.2: 'Analysis and design reflect lexical defining and real defining'.

Furthermore, we see a distinction between reflections that address the vision, main research goal, and method objectives, and reflections that target a specific method ingredient. The reflections of the former category are generic and more subjective. They can raise more method objectives and generic research questions. The reflections in the latter category are more specific and less subjective. They can serve as entry points for more specific research questions, *i.e.*, they could serve as motivation for investigating how a specific topic from cognitive science can serve as a foundation for method ingredients.

7 Related work

To our knowledge, there is no literature that clarifies how a definition of modeling method can be based on cognitive concepts. However, we found two publications that suggest it, and provide a partial demonstration.

Siau states that despite the pivotal role of modeling methods, most method designs are just based on common sense and intuition of the method designers [51]. He proposes to use cognitive psychology as a reference discipline for information modeling and method engineering. He discusses the different types of memory and knowledge from the Adaptive Control of Thought theory from Anderson [2, 1], and gives an example of how this can impact and restrict a method design. He does not concretely state how it can be used to define method ingredients. The MuDForM definition realizes explicit method objectives, and its modeling concepts are based on cognitive aspects, which demonstrates the use of knowledge from cognitive psychology as Siau suggests.

The role of cognitive aspects in the MuDForM definition resembles the idea of ontology-based metamodeling from Wand [56]. He distinguishes ontological elements and metamodel elements, and demonstrates and concludes that they can be related, but should not necessarily be the same. Wand does not state what the proper ontological elements are, nor does he define an approach for finding them. We think that the cognitive aspects in Section 5 of *the paper* can be seen as elements of an ontology of human cognition, which matches the idea of Wand.

The MuDForM definition is based on cognitive concepts from a large range of litera-

ture, cited in the reflections in Appendix A. We did not use explicit criteria for finding the right literature and the right cognitive aspects, and for deciding if they should be used in a method definition. This is a topic for future research. In this report, we wanted to sketch how cognition-based method creation can be implemented, and most of all, argue that it is possible.

8 Limitations

Following the reflection provided by Verdecchia *et al.* [55], we have identified three limitations to the validity of our study.

First, we do not make any claims regarding the completeness of the literature study, hence, we also do not do that about the completeness of the method ingredients from a cognition perspective. We think that we tackled some important authors in the field, but are aware that we missed works. For example, we think that “The Metaphors we live by” by Lakoff [33] and “How language began” by Everett [18] would be useful to study. There is simply too much literature, even for the nine years that this study took.

The second limitation is that, naturally, it was not possible within the scope of this research to study all potentially important fields of science. A mitigation to this limitation, however, is that we studied about five times more books (about 150) than the ones cited by the reflections, and these have covered other scientific fields like evolution theory, psychology, anthropology, evolutionary psychology, neuroscience, and even quantum physics.

The third limitation is that, potentially, we suffered from confirmation bias (*i.e.*, the tendency to notice evidence supporting one’s beliefs and ignore evidence contrary to one’s beliefs [47]) when we studied the literature, because we did this during the creation of MuDForM. This implies that we might have overlooked useful content from the literature, and thus, did not bookmark it. The mechanism that we used to mitigate this limitation is that we made much more bookmarks than the ones that

finally ended up in Appendix A, *i.e.*, we over-bookmarked. When we started to revisit the bookmarks, we concluded that some of them were not useful, and did not put them in the intermediate analysis document [12]. More bookmarks were rejected during the analysis stage, as described in Section 3.

9 Conclusion and Future work

This report presents the results of a qualitative data analysis on literature in philosophy, cognitive science, and linguistics. The analysis led to 69 reflection snippets, described in Appendix A. The reflection snippets are summarized around eight themes, presented in Sections 4 and 5. The starting point was the following research question: *What are common elementary cognitive concepts that people use to think and communicate, and how can they be applied in engineering a specification method?*

We have identified many cognitive concepts and showed how they can be used in the definition of MuDForM. We also conclude that cognitive science can be used to identify and drive improvements for MuDForM. Although the current version of MuDForM is quite stable and already practically applicable, there is always room for improvement. Below are some suggestions related to possible future improvements of MuDForM from a cognitive perspective. We distinguish should-haves, of which we concluded that they are an improvement, and could-haves, which require much deeper investigation to determine if they are feasible and would be an improvement.

The should-haves are:

- There should be explicit steps and guidelines for changing models, *e.g.*, merging two models. Furthermore, there could be default operations to specify what a model change entails for existing model instances.
- There should be modeling concepts to specify derived model elements.
- There should be method ingredients that directly support the specification of

location and motion.

- There should be specific method ingredients that support analogy making.

The could-haves are:

- MuDForM supports the specification of the outcome of a reasoning process. It does not support the reasoning process itself. The support of reasoning would include explicit steps, viewpoints, and guidelines, and concepts such as decision, alternative, trade-off between alternatives, and rationale behind a decision, which could be a useful addition to MuDForM.
- There are guidelines to eliminate homonyms and synonyms, and guidelines to guide the definition of model elements, their granularity, their generalizations, and in which domain they belong. We think there could be more guidance possible to reduce ambiguity in models, and in the modeling process.
- MuDForM does currently not prescribe a syntax. But just like morphology in natural language helps to understand the type of a word, it could also be applied to better understand models. There could be guidance for defining a syntax that increases the understanding of MuDForM models.
- There could be explicit guidelines to prevent that models are polluted by specific biases of involved experts. Different biases probably require different guidelines.
- It could be useful to have method ingredients that support the different speech acts. After all, making models is a speech act itself.

Appendix A contains more suggestions for future work. We did not use explicit guidelines and decision criteria for finding cognitive concepts in the literature, which itself is a topic for future research. In this report, we wanted to demonstrate how cognition-based method engineering can be implemented. But most of all, that it is possible, and that it provides a useful addition to the engineering of methods and languages for software development. It demanded us to look over the fence beyond our own expertise, which was not always easy, but very interesting and educational. We encourage you to look further, too.

A Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

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This appendix contains the reflection snippets that are the foundation for Chapters 4 and 5. Each section in this appendix corresponds to a section from those chapters. Many of the snippets suggest more research or extensions for MuDForM, which are indicated with the term ‘future work’. When a bookmark and its findings led to multiple reflections, we did not copy the bookmark and its finding, but named the bookmark and referred to it.

A.1 Research Background: Vision, Research Goals, and Method Objectives

A.1.1 Use unambiguous models to convey knowledge

Bookmark Hofstadter 1: In “Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking” [26], Hofstadter and Sander discuss that learning new concepts happens through words and through experiences. The former is seeing a word and then learning its meaning. The latter is that people learn concepts mostly through experiences, which is more frequent; some of those learned concepts get their own (compound) word.

Finding: Models are codifications of knowledge (from experiences), *i.e.*, they make tacit knowledge tangible. People might learn directly from a model by studying it. It is also possible to transform a model into, for example, software that can be executed. Such an execution can be experienced by someone, *i.e.*, an end user of the software. This means that people can learn from the model through experience, which can also be used to validate a model. Namely, when the statements from an expert are codified in a model and that model is turned into software, then the expert can validate the codification of his knowledge by experiencing the execution of the software.

Impact: Models can be used to convey knowledge, just as text. Unambiguous models can be turned into software and, when executed, used to convey knowledge through experience too. Human learning and software development coincide when knowledge is transferred through unambiguous models,

A.1.2 People care about their domain. Computers do not know what they are doing

Bookmark: In “The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language” [41], Steven Pinker discusses some consequences of the Turing machine. Such a machine can do things without understanding what it does. It can do any calculation without knowing what it stands for. For example, the syllogism ‘all men are mortal’, ‘Socrates is a man’, thus, ‘Socrates is mortal’, can be interpreted by a machine. The machine does not need to know what ‘Socrates’, ‘man’, and ‘mortal’ stand for. They can be replaced by anything when it learns to interpret ‘all’, ‘are’, ‘is a’, and ‘is’.

Bookmark: In “How the mind works” [43], Pinker reflects again on the computa-

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tional theory of mind (of Alan Turing). The brain stores and processes information. Information itself is emotionless; it is just symbols. People's minds give it meaning.

Bookmark: In “From Bacteria to Bach and Back: The Evolution of Minds” [17], Daniel C. Dennett sees the Turing machine as a mindless machine that can do computations without knowing that it is doing computations. A programmable digital computer is a universal Turing machine.

Finding: As mentioned in Appendix B, source code often contains terms of its application domain, making that code less reusable than it potentially is. In order to put only necessary knowledge in specifications, they should be defined as abstract as possible, *i.e.*, they should not be defined in terms of their application domain, but in terms of their own abstract domain, which is often a design aspect or a quality attribute domain. After all, the computer, *i.e.*, a Turing machine, does not know the semantics of what it is doing.

Impact: Software, and formal specifications in general, are like the syllogism. The computer does the calculation, but has no clue what it means outside the computer. The Turing principle and the observation that source code often contains terms from the application domain of the software, are a reason to make specifications at an abstraction level that is not based on a computer-based programming language, but on cognition-based concepts. There is no reason why human knowledge must be captured in computer-based language.

A.1.3 Specifications must mean something to people

Bookmark Harari 1: In “Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow” [23], Yuval Noah Harari explains that Homo sapiens gives meaning to the world. Most animals live in a dual layered world. They perceive the physical world with trees, rivers, rocks, and other animals, and they also perceive an inner world with things like fears, beliefs, and desires. Humans live in a triple layered reality, because they also perceive made up things like money, gods, and corporations.

Finding: It should be possible to cover things in all three layers. But, only if people can communicate about it, which is also the limitation. The method only needs to cover things that people can communicate about, which is also the case with any other specification language or natural language. Specifications themselves can also be seen as elements at the third layer. They do not really exist in the same way as elements of the first layer. They only exist as a representation in the first layer; their

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meaning is in the third layer.

Impact: The method only needs to be based on concepts of the third layer. So, no concepts for representing trees (first layer), but only concepts for representing thoughts and communication about trees. And, no concepts for representing emotions (second layer), but only concepts for thinking and communicating about emotions. The essence of a specification is what it means to people, not how it is represented. This is complementary to the observation that they mean nothing to a Turing machine, as mentioned in *Reflection 'People care about their domain. Computers do not know what they are doing'* (cf. page 39). This underpins the vision to work on specifications, *i.e.*, models.

A.1.4 Method steps and viewpoints focus the modeling process

Bookmark: In “The Organized Mind” [35], Daniel Levitin talks about active sorting, *i.e.*, separating things you need right now from things that you do not need right now.

Finding: When you are modeling, there is a lot of information. Which information is relevant at a certain moment, depends on the modeling step and viewpoint that you are working on. Some form of active sorting might offer support.

Impact: Through the steps defined by the method flow, you find which information you need to focus on at a certain moment during modeling. For example, when you model an object lifecycle, you consider different model aspects, leading to different questions to the involved domain expert, than when you are defining attributes. When you are modeling an object lifecycle of a particular domain class, you know you have to create a step for all the domain activities that the domain class has involvements in. A tool could help you to show you only those activities.

This kind of tool support can be generalized, because mostly when you are modeling, you are busy with one root element and already related model elements are possible candidates to create more detailed model content with. For example, when making a function lifecycle, you tend to only make function steps of domain activities related to the domain classes that are types of function attributes. This kind of active sorting can be automated, which improves the modeling experience.

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

A.1.5 Modeling is not an extra activity

In “Everything All at Once” [39], Bill Nye states that if you want to be successful (with a design), get in the project in the beginning.

Finding: Modeling should start from the beginning.

Impact: It does not make sense to start a modeling activity when a project already made designs in another way, or when there is already source code developed before the specification is made that the source code should comply with. Modeling should start whenever relevant (domain) knowledge is entering the project, either through some document, or through some expert. When domain models already exist and specifications, *e.g.*, requirements, must be made, then the domain models should form the terminology for those specifications.

In other words, modeling is not something you do in parallel with things you already do. It should replace (some of) them, which is captured in the guideline ‘Modeling should replace or complement other activities’.

A.1.6 Focus on domain-oriented methods

Bookmark Dennett 1: The philosopher Daniel C. Dennett states in “From Bacteria to Bach and Back: The Evolution of Minds” [17] that programming is a creative activity. Software has bugs and debugging can not be automated. Only syntax errors can be prevented. Dennett compares it to how evolution gets rid of bugs. Reproduction creates variations, and natural selection will take care of the flawed variations.

Finding: This metaphor misses an important point: getting rid of bugs through (real-life) testing, *i.e.*, ‘natural selection’, is not the only possible mechanism, because programming, unlike biological reproduction, is not a mindless activity. Programming is a cognitive activity, which can be done systematically, *i.e.*, guided by a method, to prevent bugs from happening. Dennett does not consider that. Of course, bugs can still occur. But there is more possible than testing to eliminate them.

Impact: Modeling, like programming, does not need to be a purely creative activity, where the quality of a model depends on the involved experts’ capability to formulate their knowledge. It can be guided by a method that supports the extraction of knowledge and capturing it in a way that suits the involved expert.

A program in a programming language is often the place where all decisions for

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a software system are encoded. But a programming language is not optimal for capturing most decisions in a development project. Different system aspects like security, logging, application initiation, and the application domain functionality, and development aspects like planability, time-to-market, and manageability, all have their own concepts, which could be supported by their own domain specific language (DSL). A DSL starts with a domain model. This underpins our choice to investigate a method for domain-oriented modeling.

A.1.7 Exploit the lexical hypothesis

Bookmark Levitin 1: In “The Organized Mind” [35], Daniel Levitin discusses the lexical hypothesis, *i.e.*, the most important things humans need to talk about eventually become encoded in language.

Finding: This does not only hold for peoples’ social life, but also for their work life.

Impact: It is clearly a motivation for using natural language as input for modeling, and to support the different ways of how those important things can be encoded.

A.1.8 Language awareness is innate

Bookmark: Mariano Sigman observes in the book “The Secret Life of the Mind: how our brain thinks, feels, and decides” [52] that a just born baby is already aware of spoken language, especially of their native language. *i.e.*, the language of their mother. He concludes that language awareness is innate.

Finding: Innate language awareness is a confirmation of its use in the method.

Impact: Natural language is taken into account when defining modeling concepts, which is reflected in Objective O6.

A.1.9 Cognition is more than language

Bookmark: In “The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language” [41], Steven Pinker talks about universal concepts in language. An investigation about commonalities in languages did not yield generic mental concepts that are present in all languages, but identified words and grammatical constructions that occur in almost

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

all languages. The only common thing in almost all languages is that they use sentences that have a subject, verb, and object. The mostly identified commonalities are about the presence of words.

Bookmark Pinker 1: Pinker also discusses *Mentalese*: the internal language of the mind. This is the notion that there is an internal language, which is free from syntax. For example, ‘the man throws a ball’, and ‘the ball is thrown by the man’, have a different syntax, but our mind knows they mean the same. Moreover, the mind can think without having words. People that did not learn language can still think and solve problems; just like some animals. It is a misconception that the native language of a person determines what that person can think. This misconception is called *genuine linguistic determinism*. Of course, language influences thoughts. Otherwise, language would be useless.

Bookmark Pinker 2: In “The Stuff of Thought: Language as a Window into Human Nature” [44], Pinker elaborates on *genuine linguistic determinism*, aka the *Whorfian hypothesis*, *i.e.*, that a person’s language determines what the person can think. He states this is clearly wrong as mentioned in the previous bookmark.

Finding: We conclude that it is not trivial to find cognition-based or mental-based commonalities in language. But, it does not mean that common mental concepts do not exist in the human mind. They are simply not obvious.

Moreover, besides concepts from natural language, also concepts from other cognitive, not directly language-related mental processes, should be supported by our method. In perspective, if the *Whorfian hypothesis* would be right, then the meta-model of our modeling language could be limited to the grammar of natural language.

Impact: This is a reason not only to look at natural language for finding proper modeling concepts, but also at cognitive science beyond linguistics. A specification language should be based on how people think and not just on what they talk about. This underpins the research goal.

A.1.10 Modeling concepts should be based on *Mentalese*

Bookmark Pinker 3: In “How the mind works” [43] elaborates on *Mentalese*, *i.e.*, the language of the mind, and why English is not *Mentalese*. He gives the example of people knowing relations between family members, and that monkeys also know the family relations in their group. But monkeys do not talk about it. For humans,

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a family will all its relations can be verbalized in many ways. For example, John is Mary's father, means the same as Mary is John's daughter. Moreover, there are also derived concepts like being siblings, or more specific being a sister or brother. English is not Mentalese. English sentences are cluttered with articles, prepositions, suffixes, and other grammatical boilerplate. They are needed to help get information from the mouth to the ear. But they are not needed inside one's mind.

Bookmark Pinker 4: Pinker also discusses why thoughts cannot just be represented by pictures. Pictures can be ambiguous, but thoughts, by definition, cannot be ambiguous. If a mental picture is used to represent a thought, it needs to be accompanied by a caption, a set of instructions for how to interpret the picture; what to pay attention to and what to ignore. The captions cannot themselves be pictures, or we would be back where we started. Representations can be ambiguous; also textual representations.

Finding: The method's metamodel should be based on the language of thought, *i.e.*, Mentalese. Specifications should be unambiguous, just like thoughts.

Impact: This underpins looking for modeling concepts beyond natural language, *i.e.*, concepts based on cognition. We need to investigate Mentalese.

A.1.11 Focus on mental concepts; not on the brain or reality

Bookmark Marian 1: In "The Power of Language: How the Codes We Use to Think, Speak, and Live Transform Our Minds" [36], Viorica Marian states that the notion that precise categories exist outside our interpretation of reality, may be an illusion perpetuated by language. Regardless if there are real categories that exist in the world, the linguistic and mental categories that we create, matter. They have consequences for many areas. Marian also states that mental categories do not exist inside the brain as physically separate categories.

Finding: Mental categories are the ones that should be supported in the method, because they are the basis for communication and thinking. The method should not try to attempt to cover the modeling of reality, nor should it be based on the physiological structure of the human brain. A model should reflect how people see perceive reality. This is consistent with the Reflection A.1.3: 'Specifications must mean something to people'.

Impact: How the world actually is, or how the brain is constructed, is not important for

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

a specification. Finding modeling concepts is, thus, not a matter of investigating how the brain or reality works, *i.e.*, it is not about neuroscience or physics. The method should support making models of how people perceive, think, and communicate about the world. This underpins the research goal.

A.1.12 On the evolution of thought

Bookmark Sloman 1: In “The Knowledge Illusion, Why We Never Think Alone” [53], Steven Sloman and Philip Fernbach explain that thought could have evolved for several functions:

1. To represent the world; to construct a model in our head that correspond in critical ways to the way the world is.
2. To make language possible
3. For problem-solving or decision-making.
4. For specific purposes, such as building tools or showing off to potential mates.

There is a thing in common for all these purposes:

- 5 Thought is for action; thinking evolved as an extension of the ability to act effectively. It evolved to make us better at doing what is necessary to achieve our goals. Thought is helpful for predicting the effect of actions, and to reason about actions that we did. Evolutionary seen, action came before thought.

Finding: From the perspective of creating a specification method, we conclude the following for each mentioned point above:

1. There should be a way to specify the world as it is.
2. There should be a way to translate thoughts into specifications via natural language.
3. There should be a way to specify decisions, problems, solutions, and their relation.

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4. We think that the method should not be tight to a specific purpose, but it should be possible to make a model that serves such purpose.
5. There should be a way to specify actions, and how reasoning leads to actions. It should be possible to observe the effect of actions, and use such observations in specifications.

Impact: Objective O6 reflects 2), as it underpins the link to natural language and the search for cognitive concepts, *i.e.*, concepts that make up thought. Objective O4 reflects 1) and 3). Objective O5, *i.e.*, support the specification of state, change, and their relation, addresses directly what is mentioned under 5). Regarding:

1. MuDForM offers the concepts of Context and Domain to capture ‘thoughts’ about how the world is.
2. MuDForM models are often transformations from natural language and can be translated back into natural language too.
3. MuDForM offers the concept of Features (with Functions) to reflect which actions should be taken under which circumstances. Multiple domains can be distinguished to separate problem from solution, and one can combine domains to specify how a solution solves a problem.
4. It does not make sense to put in modeling concepts for specific purposes. But of course, MuDForM can be used to model the domain of those specific purposes.
5. MuDForM offers autonomous concepts for specifying an action, *i.e.*, *Activity*, and for its *Behavioral composition* and *Lifecycle*. Each *Activity* can have pre-conditions, and each activity occurrence can have guards. *Flow structure types* (sequence, selection, parallel), and *multiplicities* (one, zero or more, at most one, at least one) offer a way to take different actions based on the constraints that are set on the flow structures.

For *Domain classes*, *Functions*, and *Domain activities*, it is possible to specify what the next actions can/must be in their *lifecycle*. By keeping track of where an instance is in its *lifecycle*, it is possible to decide what next action to perform.

A.2 Separation of Syntax and Semantics In Mind and Method

A.2.1 Concepts have meaning

Bookmark: John Searle discusses in his lectures on “Philosophy of Language” [49] the definition of concept according to German philosopher Gottlob Frege¹: a concept is a function with a truth value, and at least one argument. The statement ‘the king of France is bald’ is not a concept because it is neither true nor false. It simply does not mean anything. To be clear: baldness exists, but France does not have a king. That is why the statement is not a concept.

Finding: How does this relate to the MuDForM notion of concept?

Impact: In the definition of MuDForM, we state that a Concept is something that the human mind can give meaning to. This is a different formulation, but it covers the definition of Frege.

A.2.2 There are no colorless green ideas that sleep furiously

Bookmark: In “Syntactic Structures” [7], Noam Chomsky presents the -now famous-sentence ‘Colorless, green ideas sleep furiously’ as an example of a sentence that is grammatically well-formed, but semantically nonsensical. It is possible in natural language to write sentences that are grammatically correct, but that do not mean anything.

Impact: The metamodel enforces that feature models are expressed in terms of domain models and context models, and that domain models are expressed in terms of context models. For example, if a domain models declares that ‘someone can place an order for a book’, then a feature model has to abide this structure when using the activity ‘to place’ in a function, *i.e.*, a book and an order must be involved (and nothing else). The consequence is that feature and domain models can not be meaningless in themselves, which realizes Objective O3 (see Appendix D). Natural language and MuDForM (just as many other specification and programming languages) differ at this point.

The intention is that context models declare concepts that have a meaning outside

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gottlob_Frege

A.2 Separation of Syntax and Semantics In Mind and Method

the model. Of course, when this is not the case, then the domain and feature models that use such concepts, can also be meaningless. However, this is different from the example of Chomsky, because there, despite the meaningful words, the English grammar allows the sentence to be meaningless. With MuDForM the lack of meaning can only be caused by declaring meaningless context model elements. Regarding the example in *Reflection* ‘*Concepts have meaning*’ (cf. page 48), with MuDForM it is simply not allowed to use the phrase ‘the king of France’.

A.2.3 Meaningless symbols refer to meaningful concepts

See *Bookmark Hofstadter 1* (cf. page 39).

Impact: The cognitive aspect `Symbol` is the entry point for learning `Concepts` through words.

See *Bookmark Hofstadter 2* (cf. page 92).

Impact: From a semantics point of view, all the meaning of a model is in the meta-model, *i.e.*, in the meaning of the modeling concepts. Model elements are represented by a recognizable symbol, mostly a combination of an icon for the modeling concept and a name to point to a concept outside the model. Because the semantics of the model is defined in the metal, you can replace a name by any other name, and the model will mean the same.

See *Bookmark Levitin 1* (cf. page 43).

Impact: The cognitive aspect `Concept` reflects the notion of a concept and `Symbol` reflects the word that is used to represent its codification.

A.2.4 The mind has representations of concepts too

In “I Am a Strange Loop” [25], Douglas R. Hofstadter claims that people have a mental symbol for each concept that they know. Such a symbol is triggered whenever someone thinks about the concept. Concepts are anything that people can give meaning to; not only things represented with a noun or verb. For example, relations like ‘before’, ‘after’, and ‘but’ are also concepts, and also ‘the Eiffel Tower’, or ‘being late’ can be seen concepts.

Finding: To be cognition-based, MuDForM should also support the representation of

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

concepts with symbols. This is of course nothing new for a specification method; it is fundamental.

Impact: Concept is the root of all cognitive aspects, as represented in the diagram of Figure 2 in *the paper*. Symbol is used in the MuDForM definition to refer to a concept. It could be a mental reference, but also a reference in other contexts, like an icon or word in a model, or another type of specification. The separation of cognitive aspects Concept and Symbol resembles the notion of a concept that is represented by a mental symbol, like it is described by Hofstadter.

A.2.5 A concept can have multiple representations

See *Bookmark Pinker 1* (cf. page 44) about Mentalese not being the same as spoken or written language.

Finding: A specification requires a syntax. But the metamodel and its semantics should be defined independent of language syntax and grammar. Furthermore, it should be possible to define different syntaxes (notations and viewpoints) for specifications.

Impact: MuDForM is defined in a metamodel, which determines the semantics of MuDForM compliant models. The metamodel elements are based on cognitive aspects, which are intended to resemble the notion of Mentalese. It is possible to define multiple syntaxes and viewpoints. For example, a function lifecycle can be represented as a nested enumerated bullet list, or as a regular expression notation, or as a UML activity diagram. This is why the viewpoints are completely defined in terms of metamodel elements. They do not add extra semantics to a model.

A.2.6 Eliminate homonyms and synonyms, but not always

Bookmark Pinker 5: In “The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language” [41], Steven Pinker states that there are more homonyms than synonyms in natural languages. Homonyms are plentiful. Real Synonyms are rare.

Bookmark: In “Building a Better Vocabulary” [19] Kevin Flanigan states that a natural language does not have many real synonyms. Although two words might be seen as synonym, or a dictionary list them as synonyms, there is mostly a slight difference in the meaning, or in the context that a word is used.

A.2 Separation of Syntax and Semantics In Mind and Method

Finding: This might not apply to the terms in specifications, because there you are not always interested in all the differences between the meanings of two terms. Homonyms and real synonyms should be avoided in a specification, because they lead to unclear communication. Two terms might be synonyms, but used in different contexts by different people. Two terms might also refer to different properties of the same identity, which should be possible to model.

Different departments in an organization may use a different term for the same thing, because they consider different aspects of it. For example, employee and employment have the same identity, but refer to different properties. Vice versa, different departments might use the same word, but mean something different, for example the marketing department uses 'book' to refer to the book title, *i.e.*, the specification of the book, and the delivery department uses 'book' to refer to the instance that is shipped. Both must be supported. There should be guidelines for when to eliminate homonyms and synonyms and when to keep them.

Impact: To reduce ambiguity, eliminating homonyms and synonyms is an explicit step in the grammatical analysis. The step should be generalized to a step 'Reduce ambiguity of terms', because there are more issues of ambiguity that can be removed. There is already a guideline that says to unify terminology that expresses logical constructs, like 'for all', and 'there is'. To investigate this is future work.

Via the pattern 'Named elements' (see Section 6.1 in *the paper*), model elements can have a list of aliases, which are treated as real synonyms. Furthermore, separates classes and generalizations can be used to model different properties of the same instance. For example, 'Employee' and 'Employment contract' can be classes that each have a generalization to the class 'Employment'.

Homonyms are allowed in the sense that a named element is declared in a Specification space, *i.e.*, a name space, and across several Specification spaces, the same name might be used for different model elements as in the 'book' example above.

The MuDForM metamodel itself is normalized and does not have ambiguities in its meaning. Hence, MuDForM models are unambiguous. To benefit from this property, also the used syntax must be unambiguous. Currently, MuDForM does not prescribe such a syntax.

A.2.7 Involved experts decide about model element names, not the modeler

Bookmark: In ‘The Organized Mind’ [35], Daniel Levitin observes that humans do not have a term (word) for every concept that they can have in their mind, *e.g.*, the category ‘people that you need to notify when you are going into the hospital for three weeks’ does not have a term for it in English. This does not mean that such a concept is not understood by people.

Finding: There must be guidance for naming model elements.

Impact: Sometimes a model element has to be introduced that does not have an existing term in the domain, *e.g.*, because normalization forces you to introduce a model element which experts do not perceive as a distinct autonomous identity (yet). In such a case, a name must be invented. Such a name should be supported, preferably chosen, by the involved (domain) experts. Also, sometimes a collection of objects must get a name, because they meet some constraint, as in the example ‘people that you need to notify when you are going into the hospital for three weeks’. Also then, the involved experts should support the chosen name.

The above is reflected in the guidelines ‘The term must be recognized by the expert’ in the step ‘Eliminate homonyms and synonyms’, and ‘Involved experts choose names’ in the step ‘Model engineering’. The name of a model element is often a composition of words, and not a single word, *e.g.*, the attribute ‘book title’, or the function ‘order books online’. Furthermore, there are the guidelines ‘Use nouns for class names’, ‘Use verbs for activity names’, and ‘Let function names reflect the duration of the function’. They are clearly less important than the acceptance of the involved experts, though.

A.2.8 Resembling word forms in models

Bookmark: In “The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language” [41], Steven Pinker observes the words of a language are treated distinctly from their meaning. The sound of a word does not determine the meaning of the word, *e.g.*, a word pronounced somewhere between pet and bet does not mean something in between. But, via positioning words in a sentence, and via conjugations, meanings can be altered. For example, questions have a different word order, or the past tense has “-ed”.

Finding: The MuDForM definition separates meaning and syntax. The syntax should

not mean anything. But, syntax could be used to make it easier to understand the meaning of a modeling concept.

Impact: The current MuDForM definition does not prescribe any syntax. But, a specific implementation could benefit from the principles that natural language uses to alter the meaning of a stem term. For example, an activity 'to order a product', the class 'order', which is the result of the activity, a state 'ordered', which can be attribute value of an instance of the class 'product' or derived from an 'order step' in the object lifecycle of 'product', and the actor 'orderer', who is the one who placed the 'order'. The present participle 'ordering' can be used to indicate that an order activity is active, as in 'John is ordering Lord of the Rings', or it could be a gerund of the order activity, as in 'the ordering of Lord of the Rings by John'. There could be guidelines for resembling name correlation in the metamodel, which investigation is future work.

A.3 Supporting Analysis, Design, and their Context

A.3.1 Support analysis and design for multiple domains

Bookmark Goldberger 1: In "Why Architecture Matters" [21], Paul Goldberger states that it is the task of the architect to design the best building within the problem of the customer. Architecture must go beyond aesthetics, *i.e.*, beyond pure form. Architecture is not about itself, but about everything else. It is the job of the architect to design the best building. But society needs to provide the problems.

Bookmark: In "How to Think Like a Philosopher: Essential Principles for Clearer Thinking" [4], Julian Baggini compares thinking alone with thinking in groups. Thinking for ourselves is like turning your brain into a Swiss army knife. Your brain has to have all the required knowledge and thinking skills. Thinking together with others is like a Toolbox with dedicated tools. A Swiss army knife is compact and can do a lot. But the tool elements can not be used at the same time and are restricted by their integration in the knife. A toolbox is bigger and possibly not aligned, but can potentially do more and do it better.

Bookmark: In "Everything All at Once" [39], Bill Nye talks about good design. If the design is no good, the product will never be good. The design, including requirements, is the bottom of the system pyramid. Everything that is created after that, builds upon it. It is difficult to correct design flaws, no matter how hard you try. However, if the design is great, it is still possible to screw up later on.

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

Finding: Today's software development involves many people, who have their own distinct expertise and requirements. Developing a software system is mostly a team effort, and not the task of one or a few engineers. A development team must understand many aspects of the system and its environment. The head of an engineer is not the optimal tool to integrate knowledge from multiple stakeholders about diverse domains. Making one feature and domain model vs. making multiple feature and domain models is analogous to the army knife vs. the toolbox. There should be support for all involved (domain) experts, and their knowledge and decisions should be specified separately and integrated explicitly. MuDForM should support understanding domains, via domain models, and support creating good designs, via feature models. It should also minimize the chances that the design can be screwed up later in the development activity.

Impact: The specification of knowledge and decisions about many aspects of a system supports architecting, which is expressed by method objective O8 (see Appendix D). Furthermore, it underpins that the method should be usable for any domain (method objective O2), and it should be usable to make specifications that involve multiple domains (method objective O1).

MuDForM supports capturing knowledge and decisions from different people, about multiple domains, and supports integrating them by using model elements from one specification space in the definition of model elements in another specification space. However, there are currently no explicit concepts in the metamodel to specify transformations and consistency rules between domains and features, as mentioned in Objective O1. This is future work.

Modeling domains is an analysis activity. Modeling features is a design activity. They can be applied to functionality of the system, but also to other, non-functional, domains, like security or reliability. MuDForM models are unambiguous, hence, can be transformed into a system in an automated manner, which reduces the chances that the system contains errors that were introduced after the design. This is in general the promise of model driven development. The MuDForM modeling concepts, method steps, viewpoints, and guidelines, contribute to get a good specification, *i.e.*, a good analysis and design, which contributes to Objective O8.

A.3.2 Analysis and design reflect lexical defining and real defining

Bookmark: In "Word by Word, The Secret Life of Dictionaries" [54], Kory Stamper discusses real defining vs. lexical defining. Lexical defining is the attempt to describe

A.3 Supporting Analysis, Design, and their Context

how a word is used and what it means in a particular setting. Real defining is the attempt to declare the nature of something via defining it. Lexicographers do not undertake real defining, as they are only concerned with words that have an existing meaning.

Finding: Modelers of existing knowledge do lexical defining, which is called analysis. Modelers of 'new' knowledge, *i.e.*, design, do real defining.

Impact: The method should support capturing the existing meaning of a term, leading to a descriptive statement. It should also support declaring the meaning of a term, leading to a prescriptive statement. This is expressed through method objective O4 (see Appendix D).

A coarse grained transformation is that in a domain model we capture what something existing means, *i.e.*, a domain model is a lexical definition. However, if you are defining a new domain through a domain model, then it is a case of real defining.

In a feature model, we state what a term, *e.g.*, the name of a function, entails for the world that uses that term. As such, specifying a feature model is a case of real defining. This does not exclude that a feature is based on existing knowledge.

A context model is a form of lexical defining when it is used to refer to existing concepts, *e.g.*, physical quantities, or mathematical formalisms. When you use a context model to declare what you assume to exist outside the domains and features of interest, then it can be seen as real defining.

A.3.3 Domain models give meaning to other specifications

Bookmark: In the lectures on "Philosophy of Language" [49], John Searle disagrees with the indeterminacy of translation hypothesis of W.V. Quine [46]. Quine says that meaning depends on a reference 'coordinate system', *e.g.*, language, while Searle says that meaning exists without language. Searle says that meaning exists without the words for expressing that meaning. The argument of Quine is that you can only scientifically check the meaning through the use of words.

Finding: This discussion is related to the discussion about thoughts being independent of language, and to the notion of Mentalese (see *Bookmark Pinker 1 (cf. page 44)* and *Bookmark Pinker 2 (cf. page 44)*). Thoughts can exist without the explicit syntax that comes with a language, like in the family relations example. Primates that live in

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groups are aware of family relations, without having words to express those relations.

Impact: Specifications are not subject to discussion about meaning and language. Namely, everything meaningful and relevant should be modeled, and thus fits Quine's perspective. Furthermore, MuDForM domain models describe what can happen and what can exist. If a created domain model meets this criterion, then the situation where you want to express something that cannot be expressed with the domain model, cannot occur. If it does not meet the criterion, then the domain model is incorrect and should be adapted. This mechanism also addresses *Bookmark Dennett 1* (cf. page 42), because the obligatory use of domain models in the specification of features reduces inconsistency and prevents that specification are ambiguous.

An example: the domain model states that you can pour beer from a bottle into a glass and that the amount of beer that goes out of the bottle equals the amount that goes into the glass. This is fine. But if you also want to express (in a feature model) that beer may be spilled during the pouring, and that the amount added to the glass can be less than the amount that goes out of the bottle, then you simply made the wrong domain model. In the words of Quine and Searle [49], the meaning of the concept was there, but you did not have the language to express it.

A.3.4 Context models form a foundation for contracts with other parties

See *Bookmark Goldberger 1* (cf. page 53).

Impact: An architect uses domain models for analyzing things that must be managed and controlled with the system they are designing. They use feature models to define a design. Context models can be used for the things that already exist. Context model elements have a black box definition, *i.e.*, their externally observable signature, invariants, and preconditions and postconditions, are specified, but their implementation is not. Other parties can design (and realize) the implementation of the context model elements. A context model can serve as the foundation for a contract between the architect (and their organization) and the party that provides the implementation of the context model elements.

A.3.5 Context models support subjectivity

Bookmark: In “Fake Physics: Spoofs, Hoaxes, and Fictitious Science” [37], Andrew May posits that right and wrong are relative concepts. For example, the earth is not flat, nor is it perfectly spherical. But to call it flat is more wrong than to call it round.

Finding: Although MuDForM specifications are meant to be unambiguous, there should be a possibility to capture subjective, imprecise, and possibly ambiguous knowledge.

Impact: Capturing ambiguity and subjectivity is offered via context models. For example, if you have a criterion that you only want to buy ‘beautiful’ books, then you define a Boolean operation that determines if a book is beautiful. You can declare an Actor that has the capability to execute that Operation, which may lead to the situation that the experienced meaning of the model is ambiguous. Namely, what books are bought depends on what the assigned actor finds beautiful. However, the model itself remains unambiguous.

A.3.6 Separate what must happen from what makes it happen

Bookmark: In “The Meme Machine” [6], Susan Blackmore discusses the notion of algorithms. Many things can be seen as an algorithm. Algorithms are mindless. Algorithms are substrate neutral, which means that they can run on many things, from a computer to a human brain.

Finding: The method should support the mindlessness of algorithms, *i.e.*, having a specification of some executable logic, without specifying how it is implemented, *i.e.*, without stating what actor runs it.

See *Bookmark Pinker 9 (cf. page 87)*.

Impact: Verbs that represent actions can have an Actor that performs the action. The Actor is often omitted in the domain model, because stating what (or who) performs an action is mostly a design choice and is not in the scope of a domain model. When you develop a system, you first model what can happen, then what should happen, and after that, you want to decide what makes it happen.

MuDForM has the modeling concept Behavior modality to express if an action must or can be executed, activated (called), or just observed (received). Context models contain the declarations of Actors, including the specification of their behavior

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capabilities.

MuDForM supports making specifications without declaring the actor that does what the specification prescribes. There is an explicit transition in the modeling process, from specifying what must happen in a feature, to specifying how does it happen, *i.e.*, assigning actors to function steps. The actors are declared in a context model and their capabilities must match with the function steps they are assigned to. There is currently a gap in the metamodel to fully capture the allocation of actors to function steps. Solving the gap requires investigation in future work.

A.3.7 Formal propositions vs. propositions about something

Bookmark: In “Language, Truth, and Logic” [3], A.J. Ayer builds upon the works of Bertrand Russell and Wittgenstein. Propositions are divided into two classes: those which concern relations of ideas, and those which concern matters of fact. The former class comprises the propositions of logic and mathematics, which are necessarily true. On the other hand, propositions about empirical matters of fact are held to be hypotheses, which can be probable but never certain.

Finding: How is this division of propositions present in models?

Impact: Of course, a domain model is an example of the second class of propositions; you do your best to make a correct model, but you are never sure. It is different for a feature model. A feature model defines something that does not exist without the model. Namely, it defines what should be true in the modeled ‘reality’. A system can implement a feature incorrectly, and as such the model is an incorrect proposition of what really happens.

The first class of propositions is present in two different ways. First, formalisms, like logic and mathematics, can be embedded in context models via the formalisms pattern. This means that one can use the formalisms in models. Second, the metamodel of the MuDForM definition is itself also a formalism. For example, if you consider a step in an Object lifecycle, you always know that such a step refers to a role of a modeled Domain activity. This is not caused by the decisions of the modeler; the MuDForM metamodel forces it.

A.4 Model Engineering through Method Engineering

A.4.1 Support different types of defining a term

Bookmark Stamper 1: In “Word by Word, The Secret Life of Dictionaries” [54], Kory Stamper distinguishes different types of defining a term:

- Ostensive definition: Point to the thing. Only usable when you can point to the real world is available in some form, *e.g.*, to a picture².
- Analytical definition (aka intensional definition): Start with the genus (aka headword), *i.e.*, the core of the word. Add descriptors for differentia that clarify how the term differs from the genus. The descriptors provide criteria for determining if something can be denoted with the term.
- Synonymous defining: Listing synonyms of the term. This happens a lot, but it is not a good way to give an exact definition. (See also *Bookmark Pinker 5 (cf. page 50).*)
- Enumerative definition: special type of extensional definition that gives an explicit and exhaustive list of all the objects that fall under the concept or term in question. Enumerative definitions are only possible for finite sets and only practical for relatively small sets³.

Finding: We need to consider how the different types of defining are applicable in modeling.

Impact:

- Regarding ostensive definitions: the guidelines ‘A class description positions the class in its context’, ‘Describe a domain class’, and ‘Describe a domain activity’ state that an example instance should be given. This reflects ostensive defining.
- Regarding intensional defining: Model elements always have a modeling concept as a genus, *e.g.*, Domain class, or Attribute. The descriptors are the model element properties that are captured via the structures of the model

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ostensive_definition

³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enumerative_definition

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element. For example, car is a Class with an Attribute 'number-of-wheels' and the 'number-of-wheels' must be higher than 'two'. Furthermore, a Class can have a Generalization to a parent Class, in which the parent Classes has the role of genus, *e.g.*, a 'car' is a 'vehicle'. A Class can have more than one Generalization, *e.g.*, a 'car' is a 'vehicle', a 'status symbol', and a 'taxable object'. Depending on the domain, a different parent class can be seen as the genus of the car. Investigating if it makes sense to distinguish the genus property of a generalization is future work.

Semantics are fully defined through the metamodel. Hence, names of model elements do not express a meaning. Context model elements are an exception. They are the starting point for the definition of other elements. Their names are assumed to have meaning outside the model, *i.e.*, their internal properties are defined outside the model. Only the properties that domain model elements and feature model elements interface with, are defined in the context model.

Future work: It should be possible to change the model element of an instance, which is like changing the genus of a term. For example, if you decide to distinguish cars with four or more wheels from tricycles, and you have a car with three wheels, then you should be able to change the type of that car to tricycle.

Future work: It should be possible to specify derived elements by taking a model element as a genus and defining a constraint to determine which instances of the model element belong to the class of the derived element. For example, a 'tricycle' is a car", which 'number-of-wheels' equals 'three'. This is useful when tricycles do not have any other relevant distinguishing properties, but experts use the term in their communication.

- Regarding synonymous defining: each model element can have a set of aliases.

Future work: It should be possible to state that the instances of two model elements are the same, *i.e.*, to merge two model elements. Although real synonyms are scarce in a real-life-natural-language context, in a system development context, people from different organizational units might use different terms for the same thing. They often consider different properties of the same thing. In that case, the different terms are not exact synonyms, but it must be possible to state that (some of) their instances have the same identity. To support this is future work.

- Regarding enumerative defining: It is possible to specify classes that are enumerations of possible instances, *i.e.*, possible values.

A.4.2 Support extensional and intensional defining

Bookmark: Hofstadter and Sander discuss in “Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking” [26] the difference between the intensional and extensional defining for categories. Intensional defining is stating the properties an entity should have to belong to a category. Extensional defining is stating that an entity is a member of a category. (This is also observed in *Bookmark Stamper 1* (cf. page 59).)

Finding: Both extensional and intensional defining should be possible.

Impact: Extension is done by simply creating a new instance of a class or by the instantiating domain activity of a domain class. Stating that a domain object belongs to a domain class is not directly possible. It always goes via an explicit domain action, in which objects from a context enter a domain. For example, in a domain activity ‘to register a person as a new customer’, person data is used to create a new customer object that has attribute values that correspond to the person data. In this case, the person properties already existed outside the domain, and the register action stands for the check whether the right properties are present to be categorized as a customer, and if so, assigning those properties to a new customer object.

A.4.3 Support principles of vocabulary learning

Bookmark: In “Building a Better Vocabulary” [19], Kevin Flanigan explains five principles of vocabulary learning:

1. Definition: a word should have a definition that explains what it means.
2. Context: a word is learned by seeing how it ‘behaves’ in a context, *i.e.*, how it is used in sentences, paragraphs, and complete texts.
3. Connections: a word is related to concepts that you already know.
4. Morphology: the form of a word, *i.e.*, its parts and the conjugations can help to learn what kind of word it is.
5. Semantic chunking: cut up a word into parts that have a distinct meaning.

Finding: The principles could help when a (domain) model should be understood by someone who studies it.

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Impact: Regarding:

1. Definitions: There are guidelines for writing descriptions of model elements.
2. Context: A definition should also include an example instance of a model element, especially when it is a specification element, *i.e.*, an element that is directly contained in the specification space, such as a class, operation, actor, class relation, domain class, domain activity, domain class relation, function, or an attribute of a feature.
3. Connections: All model elements are connected to other model elements. An exception can be context elements, because they are used as references to concepts that are not fully specified. But still, those elements are in the context model, because they are needed for the definition of feature elements or domain elements.
4. Morphology: This is currently not directly supported in the MuDForM definition, because it does not prescribe a syntax. Although, it could be useful for learning MuDForM. An example is the UML syntax convention to use the same symbol for an instance as for its type, and then underline the name of the instance so you can see it is an instance. Through the structure patterns in MuDForM, a model element can be defined as a container item, a structure, an element, a reference, or a referred item, which helps to decide how it can be related to other model elements.
5. Semantic chunking: this is only supported implicitly, because it can be applied in the name of elements in structures. Currently, there are no guidelines for it. However, the names in a domain model should come from the domain. It is not the modeler who should choose the names of model elements, but the involved domain experts. It is different for function names, because they often have an invented name.

In general, it is future work to investigate what guidelines can be made to reflect the principles of vocabulary learning.

A.4.4 Avoid different ways of modeling the same meaning

See *Bookmark Pinker 4* (cf. page 45) and *Bookmark Pinker 3* (cf. page 44).

Finding: The metamodel should be based on the concepts of Mentalese as close as possible. If some meaning can be expressed in several ways with such concepts, then there should be guidelines to choose the best way. For example, a lifecycle has two types of steps: A and B. Suppose that an A should always be followed by a B, then a guideline should lead you to model this in the lifecycle model with a sequence between A and B, instead of two parallel paths, one with step A and one with step B, and a precondition on path B that it should be preceded by path A.

Impact: The MuDForM guidelines and criteria assure that models are normalized, *i.e.*, they do not have redundancies. For example, for defining (biological) family roles you only need the concepts of person, being a parent, and gender. You can specify the concepts father, mother, sibling, grandparent, cousin, etc., by expressing them in terms of parent relations and gender.

The guideline ‘Only use constraints when other modeling concepts do not suffice’ holds for the model engineering step. The special version of that guideline ‘Only use invariants if other concepts cannot cover it’ pertains to domain engineering. These are compliant with the example of paths A and B above. It is unclear how much of the modeling choices for each step are covered by the current set of guidelines. Finding out requires more investigation and is future work.

A.4.5 There should be guidelines for determining the right granularity of model elements

Bookmark Stamper 2: In “Word by Word, The Secret Life of Dictionaries” [54]”, Kory Stamper writes that lexicographers tend to fall into two categories: lumpers and splitters. Lumpers tend to give broad definitions that can cover several more minor variations on the meaning. Splitters tend to write a definition for each of those variations. A lumper’s definition might cause objects to fall under the definition while they shouldn’t. A splitter’s definition might become outdated, because the context of a term changes over time. For example, a police car was always blue, which could be in its definition. But this changed over time, and thus, the definition must be changed.

Finding: There should guidelines to determine the right granularity for the definition of a model element.

Impact: There are guidelines to determine if a model element should be split in two or more model elements, or vice versa, *i.e.*, the guidelines ‘Criterion for distinguishing

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a domain class', 'Criterion for generalizations', 'Criterion for compositions in domain models', and 'Use an abstract class for reoccurring involvements'.

However, the analogy with definitions in a vocabulary does not only pertain to the description of a model element. It is foremost the relations a model element has with other model elements. For example, if a domain class or function has two distinct lifecycle paths that are only united at the beginning and the end, then it is probably a case of lumping, *i.e.*, they should be distinct model elements. If two model elements have the same model relations, *e.g.*, the same lifecycle and the same attribute, then it is probably the same model element.

A.4.6 Guidelines for deciding which concepts become a model element

Bookmark: In "Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking" [26] Hofstadter and Sander discuss that not all categories that a person can think of need to get their own word.

Finding: There should be guidelines determining which concepts are becoming a model element, and, consequently, get their own 'word', *i.e.*, name.

Impact: There are guidelines and criteria for distinguishing domain classes, generalizations, domain activities, functions, and attributes (see *Reflection 'Guidelines for distinguishing model elements'* (cf. page 64)).

Regarding analytical definitions, described under *Bookmark Stamper 1* (cf. page 59): typically an abstract subclass gets a name that ends with the name of its parent class, *e.g.*, firetruck is a truck. For non-abstract subclasses of an abstract parent class this is less common, *e.g.*, truck is a vehicle. This is just a heuristic. There can be professional domains where the naming evolved differently, and does not follow this heuristic.

MuDForM should offer derived concepts, through which one can define a category via a constraint that completely expressed in terms of other model elements. This is future work.

A.4.7 Guidelines for distinguishing model elements

See *Bookmark Pinker 7* (cf. page 75) and *Bookmark Stamper 2* (cf. page 63).

A.4 Model Engineering through Method Engineering

There are currently a number of guidelines to determine if something should be a separate model element:

- Criterion for distinguishing a domain class
- Criterion for generalizations
- Criterion for compositions in domain models
- A domain object is an instance of precisely one concrete domain class
- Only use invariants if other concepts cannot cover it
- Activity attributes refer to classes outside the domain
- Ensure the realizability of an activity
- Objects enter a role via an action
- Use an abstract class for reoccurring involvements
- Define a function for coherent behavior that will be assigned to an actor
- Define a separate function for function steps sequences that occur more than once
- An atomic object manipulation might indicate a domain activity
- Define only used dependencies
- Only use constraints when other modeling concepts do not suffice

The description of these guidelines can be found in the full method definition [11]. We have concluded in our SLR [13] that most methods do not have so many strict guidelines. We think that there can be more guidelines for this topic, *e.g.*, for distinguishing attributes. Investigating this is future work.

A.4.8 Models represent situation-independent knowledge

Bookmark: In “Focus” [22], Daniel Goleman mentions that people can have situation-independent thought. They can reason and talk about situations that they are not in right now, or they can generalize knowledge from the situation that they are in.

Bookmark: In “How the mind works” [43], Steven Pinker reflects on quantification, and variable binding. Our compositional thoughts are often about individuals. The thought that a particular person eats an apple is different from the thought that people eat apples in general. We are capable of thinking things like ‘there is an X that Y’ without knowing such X, or things like ‘for all Xs: Y’ without knowing all Xs.

Finding: Capturing knowledge through both types of thoughts must be supported in the method. But there is no need to make a MuDForM-specific metamodel for the concepts of predicate logic, and other formalisms like calculus or propositional logic.

Of course, making specifications is capturing knowledge and making decisions about situations that occur at a different moment than the moment of specifying.

Impact: Both cases are supported during knowledge elicitation. Experts can make statements that are generic, as in ‘People can order a book, or make instance-specific statements, as in ‘John ordered Lord of the Rings’. The first case can immediately be captured in a model. The second case needs to be generalized by asking what kind of thing ‘John’ is, what kind of thing ‘Lord of the Ring’ is, what kind of thing ‘orders’ is, and what other things can ‘order’ or be ‘ordered’.

It also works the other way around. What is captured by the specification of any model element pertains to all instances of that model element. Furthermore, constraints can use the quantifiers ‘for all’, and ‘there exists’, when extra properties need to be specified for the instances of some model element.

A.4.9 Support knowledge elicitation from both semantic memory and episodic memory

Bookmark: In “A Very Short Tour of the Mind” [9], Michael Corballis writes about the notions of episodic memory and semantic memory. Episodic memory is memory for events or episodes in our lives. For example, you remember what you ate this morning. Semantic memory is memory for statements about the world. For example, to remember that Amsterdam is the capital of the Netherlands, or to remember a

word for some concept.

Finding: These notions might be relevant for modeling. But how?

Impact: The two notions of memory are relevant in the extraction of knowledge from involved (domain) experts. You can ask questions about events that happen(ed) in their domain (from their episodic memory). And, you can ask questions to let them share general knowledge about the targeted domain or system (from their semantic memory). The first type of questions lead to answers about specific instances, which can be generalized to model elements. The second type of questions will lead to answers that are already on model level.

A model can be seen as a representation of semantic memory, and when the model is executed, it creates events, which can be logged and form a representation of episodic memory. The guideline ‘Ask for examples when generic knowledge is hard to phrase’ appeals to the episodic memory of the involved expert.

A.4.10 Traceability helps to prevent falsities

Bookmark: John McWhorter discusses in his lectures “The Story of Human Language” [38] design features of human language, introduced by Charles Hockett [24], which distinguish it from animal communication.

Bookmark: In “Talking to strangers” [20], Malcolm Gladwell writes about the time that Prime minister Chamberlain went to Germany to talk to Hitler. Hitler told him that he had no plans to start a war, and Chamberlain believed him. Chamberlain did the same as what we all do when we talk to strangers. We look into their eyes and decide then if we believe them or not. Apparently, Chamberlain’s decision was incorrect.

Finding: MuDForM, and many other specification languages, have the features described by Hockett, except for the ones that are directly about auditory aspects. There is one design feature that requires reflection: Prevarication, *i.e.*, the ability to lie or deceive. When using language, humans can make false or meaningless statements. Of course, lying and deceiving is not helpful in system development and dealing with it is out of scope. But not speaking the truth is something to reckon, because several domain experts might say contradicting things about one topic, which means that some of them are not speaking the truth. It should be prevented and detected.

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Impact: Objective O7 (see Appendix D) explicitly states that modeling actions must be traceable. When domain experts give input for a modeling activity, their input can be logged. Furthermore, all the decisions can be logged in terms of the modeling concepts and steps, and followed guidelines. This means that any inconsistency somewhere in the modeling process can be traced back to the input. Of course, it is still possible that falsities end up in the model. The many consistent model viewpoints that each cover a distinct but related model aspect, and that are defined on top of one metamodel, help to detect inconsistencies in the input. Moreover, having self-contained specifications, as stated in Objective O3, makes it harder to deceive, because it prevents models to become ambiguous through the use of undefined terms.

A.4.11 Traceability and multiple viewpoints help to detect biases

Bookmark: In “The Believing Brain” [50], Michael Shermer talks about cognitive biases. A cognitive bias is a belief that something is true based on some cognitive state. For example, the belief that more people die in plane crashes than in car crashes, right after a plane crash was in the news, is called the recency bias. The book names a few, but there are many more biases⁴.

Finding: The method should help to prevent that the biases influence a specification process. This might not be equally important for all biases.

Impact: There is currently nothing in the method that actively helps to prevent biases. But, through logging of modeling decisions, specifications are traceable to statements made by involved people, which helps to prevent that specifications become affected by the modelers beliefs and the involved experts’ biases. Letting a specification be validated by others, either directly or indirectly via a translation into natural language or another representation, helps to prevent that a specification is based on the biases of one person. It is future work to investigate if it is possible to find analysis and modeling guidelines that explicitly target a specific bias. A bias in an input text that is transformed into a model, is probably also present in that model; bias in, bias out.

⁴See for example the long list and references on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cognitive_biases

A.5 Match Reality with Useful Categories

A.5.1 Categories enable inference of properties

Bookmark: In “How the mind works” [43], Steven Pinker concludes that the mind has to get something out of forming categories. That something is inference. Obviously, we can not know everything about every object. But we can observe some of its properties, assign it to a category, and from the category predict properties that we did not observe. If Mopsy has long ears, he is a rabbit; if he is a rabbit, he should eat carrots, go hippity-hop, and breed like, well, a rabbit.

Finding: Categorizing a thing should enable you to infer properties of the thing that are captured in the definition of the category.

Impact: If you know an instance of a *Classifier*, e.g., *Domain class* or *Domain activity*, then it must have values for the specified properties of that *Classifier*. If it does not, then either the *Classifier's* definition is incorrect, the classification is incorrect, or your knowledge about the instance is incorrect (or incomplete). Correct the model or the instance such that the consistency between them is ensured. This reasoning is captured in the modeling guideline ‘Ensure consistency between classifiers and known instances’.

A.5.2 Prevent mismatches between reality and model

Bookmark: In “The Stuff of Thought: Language as a Window into Human Nature” [44], Steven Pinker stresses the importance of good definitions of concepts. He uses the insurance policy that covers the attack of 9-11-2001 as an example. There was a discussion whether the attack is one or two events? This is relevant because the insurance policy was up to \$3.5 billion per event. So, depending on the attack being one or two events, \$3.5 billion or \$7 billion are paid. Apparently, the definition of ‘event’ was too broad to get a statement whether it was one or two events.

Finding: In the example, the definition of event was apparently too broad to simply decide whether it was one or two events. The insurance domain model should help to clarify whether the twin towers are one or two insured objects, and what the time span of one event can be. Besides the definition of event, also definitions of concepts like causation and effect of an event could be relevant for the specification of the insurance policy.

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It is impossible to specify a concept in the real world completely, as mentioned under *Bookmark Pinker 7* (cf. page 75). Concepts that are an instance of a specification do not have that problem. A specification of a concept can be seen as a complete specification of that concept. For example, if a car is defined as a thing with wheels, then a bicycle and a shopping cart are also cars. This is okay if only the wheel-having property is important. But if you want to know how many passengers it can transport, it is clearly an incomplete definition.

The method should help to minimize the mismatch between model and reality. It should ensure consistency across model elements. Relevant instances, including their properties, must unambiguously fit the model elements.

Impact: The cognitive aspect *Entity* stands for concepts that have an identity. MuD-ForM offers the possibility to relate a model element to other model elements: it can be a whole, and it can be part of other elements, it can be a generalization or a specialization of other elements, it can be the type of other elements, and it can be in a constraint specification together with other elements. All the possible relations are defined in the metamodel, derived from the cognitive aspects model (see Section 5 of *the paper*), and listed in Table 1 in Section 6.3. There are guidelines for determining if something is a separate *Classifier*, e.g., *Domain class* or *Domain activity* (see *Reflection 'Guidelines for distinguishing model elements'* (cf. page 64)).

Our experience is that having one metamodel, explicit steps and viewpoints, and clear guidelines, helps to achieve a coherent and consistent set of model elements. Especially the analysis coherency between state (objects) and change (actions), when analyzing the object lifecycle of a *Domain class*, minimizes mismatches between the real world and the model.

A.5.3 Classifiers must represent functional categories

Bookmark: In “The Organized Mind” [35], Daniel Levitin discusses the notion and importance of categorizing: perceptual and conceptual. We categorize things because they look, sound, smell alike. But also because they can fulfill some function in some context. The latter categories are called functional categories.

Finding: MuDForM should support the detection of functional categories. Objects do not belong to the same category because they look (or sound, or smell) the same, but they are the same because you do the same things with them. Vice versa, objects belong to a different category when you do something different with them, *i.e.*, they

undergo different types of actions.

Impact: MuDForM has several guidelines driven by the notion of functional categorizing: ‘Criterion for distinguishing a domain class’, ‘Criterion for generalizations’, ‘Criterion for compositions in domain models’, ‘Activity attributes refer to classes outside the domain’, ‘Ensure the realizability of an activity’, ‘Use an abstract class for recurring involvements’, ‘Objects enter a role via an action’, ‘Define a function for behavior that will be assigned to an actor’, and ‘Define a separate function for function steps sequences that occur more than once’. These guidelines also take care of normalization of a model. (See also the guidelines in *Reflection ‘Guidelines for distinguishing model elements’* (cf. page 64).)

A.5.4 Support multiple functional categories for one instance

Bookmark: In “The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language” [41], Steven Pinker observes that similarity is in the eye of the beholder. Similarity does not only depend on the properties that two things share, but also on who makes the comparison and when. Consider a piece of baggage at an airport. A spectator might see shape, color, and brand. The pilot is more considered with the weight, and the passenger with destination and ownership. Which two pieces of baggage are more alike is different for each of those three people.

Finding: This related to the notion of functional categories as mentioned in *Reflection ‘Classifiers must represent functional categories’* (cf. page 70). Objects do not belong to exactly one category. In the example, it must be possible to consider one piece of baggage from the perspective of three categories.

Impact: MuDForM allows classifying objects throughout their life with different classifiers. The notion of abstract and concrete subclass is derived from the cognitive aspect Identity. When an instance is created, it gets an identity from exactly one concrete classifier. But the instance can be categorized by multiple abstract classifiers. In the model, these classes must be related to the concrete class, either as subclass or as parent class. In the example, a concrete, *i.e.*, non-abstract Class ‘piece of baggage’ can have three abstract subclasses: ‘physical object’ for spectators (which does not make much sense), ‘piece of cargo’, and ‘owned baggage’. Each subclass considers different properties.

A.5.5 A model is a complete specification of the world it describes

Bookmark: in “How the mind works” [43], Steven Pinker says that the rules of common sense are very hard to write down, and to derive. He gives three examples:

1. If there is a gallon of milk in a bottle and the bottle is in the car, then there is a gallon of milk in the car. But when there is a gallon of blood in your body, and your body is in the car, it would be strange to claim there is a gallon of blood in the car.
2. A car seat is a chair, and a chair is furniture, but it would be strange to say that a car seat is furniture.
3. If you open a jar of peanut butter, your head will not evaporate.

An intelligent being has to deduce the implications of what it knows. But only the relevant implications. This is a challenge for robot design and for epistemology.

Finding: The examples address the discrepancy between concepts, *i.e.*, meaning, and their wording. Strictly seen, there is a gallon of blood in the car, and you can put a car seat in your house as furniture. You even don't know for sure that your head will not evaporate (coincidentally) at the same moment you open a jar.

Impact: With MuDForM, just as with any other specification method, you specify what you find relevant. For example, if you do not model that people have a shoe size, then, in your perception of the world, they do not have it.

MuDForM is not a deduction engine, not does it magically add “common sense” to specifications. But a model contains relations between concepts, which can be used in a deduction about instances that comply with the model. Regarding example 2, if you model that all car seats are chairs, and all chairs are furniture, then indeed a car seat is furniture. It is possible to specify constraints on generalizations, *e.g.*, ‘a chair is only furniture if it stands in a room and is available to sit on’. As a result, a car seat is not furniture when it is stored in a warehouse of car parts, but it is when it stands in your living room for people to sit on.

A.5.6 It must be unambiguously determinable if an object belongs to a category

Bookmark: in “How the mind works” [43], Steven Pinker says that humans put things in categories to apply the knowledge about similar objects to another object. But it is very hard to define a category precisely. The bachelor example is mentioned again (see *Bookmark Pinker 7* (cf. page 75)).

Finding: If there is no clear definition of a category, then it is not possible to unambiguously deduct if an object belongs to the category. If the category bachelor is not precisely defined, which is the case, then knowing that someone is a bachelor can only be achieved by stating that the person is a bachelor.

Impact: Instances of model elements are created via Classifiers. Objects (or anything with an identity) can be allocated to multiple Classifiers. These classifiers must be related in the model. Otherwise, the semantics of saying that an object belongs to several categories is not clear.

The instances of MuDForM models, can only undergo a change of state via an action. So, making someone a bachelor has to happen in a specific action, e.g., to divorce. Another option would be that the bachelor state can be derived from other properties, but this requires a precise specification of the bachelor category is.

A.5.7 Different objects in the real world can correspond to one model instance

Bookmark Searle 1: John Searle discusses in his lectures on “Philosophy of Language” [49] Leibniz’s law: two objects are identical if and only if they have the same properties.

Finding: How does Leibniz’s law manifest itself for instances of a MuDForM model? Do they follow the same rule?

Impact: It depends. An object in Leibniz’s law corresponds to an instance of the cognitive aspect `Entity`. If an entity is purely conceptual and only exist as instance of a model, then two entities with the same properties are indeed the same entity, because the entities only exist as instance of a model, and as such can only have properties that are defined by the model. If the entities are physical, and they have the same properties through the eyes of the model, then they might not be the

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same in the real world. Namely, you might not have modeled all the ‘real-world’ properties. See the example of the hunter’s arrows in *Bookmark Pinker 6* (cf. page 74). A distinguishable arrow is an `Entity`. An indistinguishable arrow is just a `Concept`, which becomes an `Entity` when if it is identifiable, e.g., by a distinguishable visual mark on the arrow.

A.5.8 Objects differ if and only if they are distinguishable

Bookmark Pinker 6: In “The Stuff of Thought: Language as a Window into Human Nature” [44], Steven Pinker discusses that some indigenous languages only have number words for one, two, and many, in which even two stands for ‘a couple’ and not exactly two. These people do not need to count more, because they keep track of individual items. For example, in a hunter-gatherer tribe that is investigated, hunters keep track of individual arrows that they have. So, they do not need to count them. They know which arrows they have fired, and which ones not.

Finding: The example illustrates that objects can be counted, and compared via their attributes. If you cannot distinguish your arrows, you cannot say which arrow you have fired.

Impact: If you distinguish your arrows, then they are domain objects with their own identity and state, hence, ‘Arrow’ is a *domain class*. If you can not distinguish them, and can only count them, then ‘Arrow amount’ is a *context class*. In such case, ‘Quiver’ can be a *domain class* with an *attribute* ‘Number of arrows inside’ with the *class* ‘Arrow amount’ as type.

This is also related to Leibniz’s law, as mentioned in *Bookmark Searle 1* (cf. page 73). When two arrows can not be distinguished, they are the same thing. However, in a collection they can be distinguished by their position and thus can be counted. If you shake the quiver, you can not determine with certainty which arrow was where before the shaking.

Impact: MuDForM offers a few default values for multiplicities: zero or more, one, at most one, or at least one. It could be possible to add something similar to ‘a couple’, like in the example of the hunter’s arrows. For example, a car can have many wheels, but typically four or six is the maximum. So, being able to say that a car has ‘a couple’ of wheels could be useful. It is ambiguous what the formal semantic difference with ‘at least one’ is, but the differences can be meaningful to people. Typically, when there are only a couple of objects, they are distinguishable, e.g., the left front wheel of

the car, or my best long-distance arrow.

A.5.9 Objects are not tied to one category

Bookmark Spinoza 1: In “The Giants of Philosophy” [34], Charlton Heston narrates about Spinoza. Spinoza rejects the view of ancient philosophers that things have an essence, *i.e.*, each thing belongs to one category that defines its essential properties. He rejects it, because a thing can undergo many changes, resulting in different properties, while maintaining its identity. Second, imagination and perspective are very unreliable.

Bookmark Pinker 7: Steven Pinker observes in “Words and Rules” [42] that People think in categories. People make abstractions, *i.e.*, categories, and recognize an object as belonging to a category. Pinker even states that to understand mental categories is to understand much of human reasoning. We are not dumbfounded by every new turtle we see. We categorize it as a turtle and expect it to have certain traits, like being slower than a hare, or having a shell. Concepts in the mind pick out categories in the world. The simplest explanation of concepts is that they are conditions for membership in a category, a bit like definitions in a dictionary. These are called classical categories; a notion that was challenged by Ludwig Wittgenstein. (Remarkable is that Pinker assigns the statement that the notion of classical categories is wrong to Wittgenstein, but that Lang *et al.* [34] state that Spinoza already made that statement centuries earlier (see *Bookmark Spinoza 1 (cf. page 75)*).

It is difficult and sometimes impossible to define categories in the classical way. The example of ‘bachelor’ is given. Is the pope a bachelor? Is a one-month-old boy? Is a man of 90 years old whose wife has just died? etc. Categories often have prototypes; a sparrow is a better example of a bird, than a penguin.

Bookmark: Hofstadter and Sander observe in “Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking” [26] that categories are very widespread. Not only physical things, or an abstract concept like love defines a category, but also the concept of ‘But’ can be seen as a category. It is repeatedly stated that categories as a clear box is very misleading, because things do not belong in precisely one box.

Finding: The notion of category must be supported. But objects should not be tied to one category. They can initially be created from a class, *i.e.*, a type. But it should also be possible to change the categorizations of an object.

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The problem of deciding if a thing in the world belongs to a specific category is less present in a system/world that is governed via specifications made in a specification language. Namely, a thing is a member of a category if you state it is. The specification problem is defining as accurate as possible what the criteria for membership are. The modeling language and the guidelines should help in defining a concept, *i.e.*, a model element.

Impact: The cognitive aspect Category represents category as meant by Pinker. Category is a subclass of Concept. It is implemented via the modeling concept *Classifier*, which can have *Generalization* relations to other *Classifiers*. *Classifiers* can have instances, *i.e.*, values and objects, and events and actions.

In MuDForM, like in many other specification and programming languages, instances are created from a type, which gives them a set of predefined properties. It is possible that those properties change over time. MuDForM currently covers this by relating the types to each other. For example, a person can become a customer, which means that they can have a customer account, or a person can become an employee, which means they get a salary. In this case, the class Person is a generalization of both the class Customer and the class Employee.

All aspects in the cognitive aspects model (Figure 2 of *the paper*) are a subclass of concept. This implies that an instance of any cognitive aspect can also be an instance of any other cognitive aspect. For example, a thing that is seen as an action, can also be seen as an object. In the MuDForM metamodel, this perspective is reflected via the class Classifier. Objects can become attributes of another object via domain actions. Or attributes can be transformed into objects. Note that typical (OO programming) languages do not allow objects to change their class.

The current method definition does not provide operations to change the type of an instance. Investigating what operations are needed is future work. Domain objects can be assigned to a different type, *i.e.*, be assigned to another domain class, while retaining meaning, as long as the new domain class has attributes that refer to the same attribute types (or subclasses thereof). For example, an instance of the domain class Employee with the name John can be retyped to Person with the name John, as long as they refer to the same context class Name. Retyping objects requires modeling concepts that reflect what to do with instances when their type changes. Retyping is for example needed when domains are integrated, *e.g.*, when two domain class instances are identified as the same object when their domain classes are unified.

It should also be possible to state that an object is itself also a class. Then the step

from metamodel to model becomes recursive, *i.e.*, there is no difference between model as a type and a model as an instance. There are only instances that comply with a model. Such a model could be called a metamodel, if its instances are models themselves. Enabling this is future work.

A.5.10 There are no exact category definitions in the real world

Bookmark: In “How the mind works” [43], Steven Pinker refers to the book “Women, Fire, and Dangerous Things” [32] by George Lakoff named after a fuzzy grammatical category in an Australian language. Lakoff argues that pristine categories are fictions. They are artifacts of the bad habit of seeking definitions, a habit that we inherited from Aristotle and now must shake off.

Finding: This is similar to the bookmarks in which the authors referred to Spinoza (*Bookmark Spinoza 1 (cf. page 75)*) and Wittgenstein (*Bookmark Pinker 7 (cf. page 75)*), who claimed that things do not belong to an exact category. But that does not mean that categories are not useful.

In the light of a model and its instances: you cannot talk about instance properties that you did not define in the model. So, it must be possible to define a model that can capture all relevant properties of all relevant instances. This implies that it should be possible to generalize instance properties and capture them in a category, and it should be possible to give instances extra properties that are captured in another category, where the latter category has as property that its instances also belong to the first category.

Impact: A Classifier has a Generalization structure, which contains Generalizations. The modeling concept Generalization is based on the cognitive aspect characteristic of Concept, which is described in Table 2 in *the paper*. For example, being a car is a characteristic of being a firetruck. This might seem counter-intuitive, but it is the same for the gray haired example (see *Bookmark Baggini 1 (cf. page 84)*). Being a gray haired cat, *i.e.*, belonging to the category of gray haired cats, is the same as being a cat with gray hairs, *i.e.*, being a cat that has the characteristic of a gray hair.

A.6 Time is Perceived through Events

A.6.1 Events are ordered in time, and have a duration

Bookmark Pinker 8: In “The Stuff of Thought: Language as a Window into Human Nature” [44], Steven Pinker observes that time is encoded in grammar in two ways. First, in tense, *i.e.*, past, present, and future. The other is called aspect, which is about the shape of the event. For example, instantaneous, as in "swat a fly", open-ended, as in "running around", a marking completion, as in "draw a circle". These are often confused in language, but are conceptually different. There is a third one is needed: reference time, *i.e.*, an event to which is referred. For example, I ate before I showered, in which, I showered is the reference time.

Finding: Regarding tenses: it must be possible to relate the execution time of one event relative to the execution time of any other event. The shape of events must also be covered in specifications.

Impact: The cognitive aspects model (see Section 5 in *the paper*) has an order relation between Events. There is also the relation changes between Action and Object, which has a timing aspect, as one can speak of the moment before and after an action, and can consider how the object is changed. Regarding the event shape: an *Activity* can be atomic or non-atomic. Actions that are an instance of an atomic activity have a timestamp by definition. Instances of non-atomic activities always have a starting time, and if they are finished, they also have a stopping time.

A.6.2 The past is determined by the events that have happened

Bookmark Sigman 1: Mariano Sigman observes in “The Secret Life of the Mind: how our brain thinks, feels, and decides” [52] that in most languages, the future is in front of us and the past is behind us, *i.e.*, we move forward and leave the past behind. But in the language Aymara⁵, it is the opposite. The past is in front of us, because you can see it. The future is behind us, because you cannot see it.

Finding: Seeing the future or past being in front or behind us does not any impact on the MuDForM definition. Time is perceived through events. The notion of time needs to be present in the method. It should be possible to see what happened in the past and to see what will or can happen in the future.

⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aymara_language

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Impact: The cognitive aspect Event is the anchor for time. There is no time without events. Events can be logged and have timestamp. There are three modeling concepts that cover Event and its derivative cognitive aspect Action: *Operation*, *Domain activity*, and *Function*.

A.6.3 Lifecycles enable stepping through time

See *Bookmark Pinker 8* (cf. page 78) and *Bookmark Sigman 1* (cf. page 78).

Impact: MuDForM does not provide in tense. But, object lifecycles and function lifecycles (flows), allow, as a matter of speaking, to virtually travel through time. An object and function execution are always at some point in their lifecycle. One can speak of the steps that happened, the steps that happen now, and the steps that might or must happen. The flow structure pattern, which is the foundation for lifecycles offers several possibilities to order events in time, e.g., sequential or parallel, optional or obligatory, which allow you to consider what can happen next. It also allows simulating what to do next and what the impact of that action will be. Via logging of all the things that already happened, it is also possible to see the past.

It is also possible to let the start or end of an action depend on a constraint. Such a constraint can be expressed in terms of another event. To make a flow executable, constraints on the starting or stopping of an action, which involve other events, must be after those events. For example, you can not specify ‘start cooking two hours before dinner’. Simply because you do not know if and when the dinner will happen. Of course, saying ‘start cooking two hours before you planned to have dinner’ is possible.

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A.7.1 Language is common, but there is no common language

Bookmark: John Searle expresses his doubts about Chomsky’s universal grammar [8] in his “Philosophy of Mind lecture series” [48]. He mentions that Chomsky has weakened the claim that humans have innate principles for acquiring language, instead of hard innate rules for languages, which Searle finds more plausible. The debate about the nature of a language acquisition device in our brain is still going on. There are also no rules identified that all linguists agree on.

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Finding: We conclude that the method should be based on principles that are common across most languages, and the mental principles that enable language acquisition. The fact that this is not 100% possible does not disqualify the idea.

Impact: Objective O6 states that the concepts on which the method should be based are not limited by natural language. Natural language is a starting point. Cognitive concepts, in this case the ones that are needed to acquire language, are more fundamental, which is reflected in Objective O6

A.7.2 Support for words that are common in all languages

Bookmark: In 'How the mind works' [43], Steven Pinker says that all human cultures ever documented have words for the elements of space, time, motion, speed, mental states, tools, flora, fauna, and weather, and logical connectives (not, and, same, opposite, part-whole, and general-particular).

Finding: Some of the mentioned word categories should be supported directly in the metamodel; some seem to be too domain-specific for a generic specification method.

Impact: All the mentioned words can be processed during Grammatical Analysis. But they are not supported equally.

'Not', 'and', and 'same' are directly supported, either via a structure or in a constraint. Part-whole is supported via Attributes. General and particular are supported via Generalization and instantiation. Opposite supported via ordered enumerations, like in 'small, medium, large' where small is the opposite of large. When there are only two possible values, then the opposite concept is the same as 'not'.

Space is currently not supported, but via Attributes and Activities roles, motion and location can be expressed. As mentioned in *Reflection 'Support specification of location, force, agency, and causation'* (cf. page 85), it makes sense to support motion and location more directly.

Mental states are not supported, because that would make MuDForM tied to the topic of human conditions, which clearly goes too far. Tools, flora, fauna, and weather can be seen as specific domains, which could be modeled using the provided modeling concepts.

A.7.3 Support part of speech concepts

Bookmark: In “Word by Word, The Secret Life of Dictionaries” [54], Kory Stamper refers to the general concepts of part of speech. In English, the main parts of speech are noun, pronoun, adjective, determiner, verb, adverb, preposition, conjunction, and interjection.

Finding: It makes sense that the method supports the part of speech concepts. Unless there is a reason not to.

Impact: During grammatical analysis, the different part of speech concepts become model candidates in the following way:

- Noun → Class (or one of its subclasses), or Attribute, or sometimes a feature.
- Pronoun → Function attribute, typically at feature level.
- Adjective → value of Attribute, or sometimes a subclass. See example about gray hair (see *Bookmark Baggini 1* (cf. page 84)), which can be modeled as a value of an Attribute hair color, or as a Class of gray haired cats.
- Determiner: This depends on the type of determiner:
 - Definite article → an Attribute, typically of a Function.
 - Indefinite article → an Involvement in an Activity, or a declaration of a Function attribute.
 - Quantifier → Either in the definition of a constraint, or the quantified property is in the definition of a classifier that pertains to the quantifier itself.
 - Demonstrative → an Attribute, typically of a Function or a Domain activity.
 - Possessive → Attribute, or Life dependency.
- Verb → Activity, *i.e.*, Operation, Domain activity, or Function.
- Adverb → value of Attribute of an Activity, or sometimes as sub-Activity.
- Preposition → Activity role, or Attribute, or Life dependency.
- Conjunction: This depends on the meaning of the conjunction. ‘and’ and ‘or’ indicate a static structure of some Classifier. ‘but’, ‘while’, and ‘because’ indicate a Constraint.

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- **Interjection:** It does not make sense to have a modeling concept for this. Interjections are hardly used in system specification texts.

So, all all relevant part of speech concepts can be handled. Some are supported by guidelines. There could be better guidelines when the transformation is not straightforward. For example, in the gray hair example (see *Bookmark Baggini 1* (cf. page 84)), it is not clear from the text which transformation should be chosen. But there could be guidelines for it, making the grammatical analysis process more systematic. Detecting and formulating them is future work.

A.7.4 Support modeling verbs, and their temporal contour

Bookmark: Hofstadter and Sander observe in “Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking” [26] that verbs are also labels of categories.

Bookmark: In ‘The Stuff of Thought: Language as a Window into Human Nature’ [44], Steven Pinker writes that linguists sort verbs in classes based on their temporal contour. There are verbs for states, like ‘knowing an answer’ or ‘being in Amsterdam’, in which nothing changes. There are verbs for events in which something happens. Events are divided into those that can go indefinitely, like ‘running around’ or those that have an end point, like ‘winning a race’. The end point indicates a change of state.

Verbs are also divided by whether they describe an event that is durative or instantaneously. There are also iterative verbs, like ‘pound a nail’, or verbs for the inception of state, like ‘sit down’.

Finding: It should be possible to see verbs as categories. The different verb classes must be supported, unless there is a reason not to.

Impact: Event and its subclass `Action` are the cognitive aspects that reflect verbs. MuDForM has the metaclass `Activity` as a `Classifier` which can have instances that express `Events`. `Operation` instances reflect `Events`. Instances `Domain activities` and `Functions` reflect `Actions`, because they also involve a state change to one or more `Objects`.

Verbs for states are captured in different ways: via `Attributes` (the car is blue, or the car has a blue color), via instances of `Classes` (John is a man), via `Generalizations` (cars are vehicles), via `Class relations` (the glass stands on the table, in which a stand

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relation exists between the glass and the table). Grammatical analysis has two Phrase types for state-oriented verbs: the ISA phrase, *i.e.*, state structure phrase state phrase, and the HAS phrase, *i.e.*, static structure phrase. There are guidelines for deciding how to model verbs that express a state.

Verbs that indicate an event can be modeled as Activities, *i.e.*, as Operations, Domain activities, or Functions. All actions, *i.e.*, instances of Activities, are started explicitly. If the actual starting is not in scope, then observing that an action has started is the instantiation of the action. There are guidelines for deciding if an event verb is classified as an Operation, Domain activity, or Function.

Duration of actions is supported in two ways. Domain activities can be atomic or non-atomic. Non-atomic actions have an explicit starting moment, and, if they complete, have an explicit stopping moment. Atomic actions are either completed or non-completed. Physically they take time, but conceptually not. For example, when you order a book online, it takes time to process the order in the software system, but you either ordered or did not order the book. The domain activity ‘to order’ is atomic. The whole online steps you go through of selecting a book title, is typically a Function and is not atomic. Operations, which are context model elements, are always atomic, because they are executed outside the scope of the domain and feature model.

A.7.5 Support to be, to have, to do, and to go

Bookmark: In “Words and Rules” [42], Steven Pinker observes that the verbs to be, to have, to do, and to go, are present in most languages. Many language scientists believe that the meanings of these verbs, *i.e.*, existence, possession, action, motion, are at the core of the meaning of all verbs. For example, the mind treats telling him a story as causing the story to go to him, resulting in him having it.

Finding: There should be a modeling concept for each of the mentioned verbs, unless there is a reason not to.

Impact:

- Existence (to be) is reflected in 1) instantiation, *e.g.*, the object ‘my car’ is an instance of the class ‘car’, 2) in Generalizations, *e.g.*, a ‘car’ is a ‘vehicle’, and 3) in Attributes, *e.g.*, ‘my car is blue’ can be modeled by giving the class ‘car’ an attribute ‘color’, and stating that the ‘color’ of ‘my car’ is ‘blue’. (See also *Reflection ‘Support different meanings of to be’ (cf. page 84).*)

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- Possession (to have) is reflected via 1) Attributes, *e.g.*, ‘my car’ has ‘four wheels’, and 2) via object life dependency, *e.g.*, an ‘order’ is dependent on a ‘customer’, which means that an order can not exist without a customer who placed the order.
- Action (to do) is reflected via the concept activity, *e.g.*, a Domain activity ‘to place an order for a customer’, or a Function ‘order books online’.
- Motion (to go) is currently not reflected directly. But, function flows can capture that an object that just participated in one step, can then participate in another step. Another kind of motion is the reaction to events, and the creation of events, which denote interactions with the context of a function execution. It is an option to support the notion of motion, and location, with specific modeling concepts. This requires more investigation in future work. (See also *Reflection ‘Support specification of location, force, agency, and causation’* (cf. page 85).)

A.7.6 Support different meanings of to be

Bookmark Baggini 1: In ‘How to Think Like a Philosopher: Essential Principles for Clearer Thinking’ [4], Julian Baggini talks about the four different meanings of the English verb ‘to be’:

1. To be An instance of something; Felix is a cat.
2. To have a property; Felix is Furry.
3. To be Somewhere; Felix is in his basket.
4. To mean something; To be a cat is to be free.

Some languages have different verbs for each of these meanings. There is a strong coherence between being an instance and having a property. For example, Felix is a gray haired cat (meaning 1) vs. Felix has gray hair (meaning 2).

Finding: The different meanings of ‘to be’ should be supported in the grammatical analysis. There is no intrinsically correct model of ‘is a’ (meaning 1) and ‘has a’ (meaning 2). But there should be guidelines to help to decide how to model it.

Impact: There are guidelines during grammatical analysis for deciding how to represent the different meanings of ‘to be’.

A.7 Building Modeling Concepts from Natural Language

The guideline ‘Criterion for distinguishing a domain class’ helps the modeler to make a decision if something should be modeled as a generalization to a separate class (meaning 1), or as an Attribute (meaning 2). In the example, should you define Domain classes ‘gray haired cat’ and its generalization ‘cat’, an Attribute ‘hair color’ with ‘gray’ as possible value, or even a boolean attribute ‘gray haired’? If gray haired cats are related to specific activities, which are not related to cats in general, then you should define separate classes for them. If there are many possible colors, and there are no different, related domain activities for each color, then model an Attribute ‘hair color’ of the class ‘cat’. If only the color gray is relevant for some activity that is related to the class ‘cat’, then model the boolean attribute.

Meaning 3 is not directly supported, because there are no concepts yet for modeling locations. It can be covered by either an Attribute ‘location’ with a possible value ‘his basket’ when basket is not a domain class, or by a relation between domain class ‘cat’ and ‘basket’ in case ‘basket’ is a domain class.

Meaning 4 is addressed via the same reasoning as for meaning 1 and 2. So, via a generalization or via an attribute.

A.7.7 Support specification of location, force, agency, and causation

Bookmark: In “How the mind works” [43], Steven Pinker observes that location in space is one of the two fundamental metaphors in language. It is used for thousands of meanings. The other metaphor is force, agency, and causation.

Finding: As these metaphors are widespread, we see them as candidates for cognitive aspects.

Impact: Agency is covered by the cognitive aspect Agent. An Agent may perform Events, which reflects force. Force is implicitly also present in the order relation, *i.e.*, if a specification states that one Event must be followed by another, then this can be seen as an expression of force. Also, the combination of an Agent perceiving an Event, followed by that Agent performing an Event can be seen as force. Causation is simply covered by the causes relation.

Location in space is not covered yet. But, as mentioned in *Bookmark Pinker 10 (cf. page 89)*, it maybe should. Location can be a subclass of Concept with relation Concept is at Location. Then the cognitive aspect Movement can be a subclass of Event with relation Movement of Concept, and optional relations Movement from

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

Location and Movement to Location. Extending the cognitive aspects, and the derived modeling concepts, with location and movement is future work.

A.7.8 Support different types of speech acts

Bookmark: In the lectures on “Philosophy of Language” [49], John Searle discusses if the different types of speech acts can also be done with pictures. The types are assertive, directive, commissive, expressive, and declaration.

Finding: Should the different types of speech acts be covered by MuDForM, and, if so, how?

Impact: MuDForM does not prescribe a textual or graphical notation. We think that that all metamodel concepts can have both. The relation between the modeling concepts and the different classes of speech acts is not straightforward, but we can observe the following:

- Assertives are expressed through a domain model, because a domain model describes what can happen and what can exist. Explicitly stating a collection of instances of domain activities and domain classes, can be seen as an assertive.
- Directives are present in a different way. Function flows express what must happen. So, given that a Function is activated, the Function’s specification states what must happen, which can be seen as a directive.
- Commissives, which state what a result will be, can be expressed as post-conditions of Activities.
- Expressives, which state emotions, are not covered, because specifying emotions does not match with the purpose of a specification. Of course, it is possible to model the domain of emotions.
- Declarations, is the main type of speech act that is covered. Namely, a model declares what types of things can exist and happen.

The mentioned modeling possibilities do probably not cover the full spectrum of speech acts. More investigation is needed to identify new modeling concepts and guidelines to address the specification of speech acts. This is a suggestion for future work.

A.7.9 Support Subject-Verb-Object sentences

Bookmark Pinker 9: In ‘The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language’ [41], Steven Pinker discusses that almost all languages have subject-verb-object (SVO) as the basic structure of a sentence; not necessarily in that order.

Finding: The method should seamlessly deal with this.

Impact: MuDForM complies with the SVO structure. The phrase type ‘interaction structure’ expresses a change to one or more objects. The format is: *(subject) TO verb object (preposition object)**. The verb from this type of phrase typically becomes an Operation, a Domain activity, or a Function.

A.7.10 Compound names correlate with hierarchy between concepts

Bookmark: In “The Organized Mind” [35], Daniel Levitin observes that all languages and cultures independently came up with naming principles so similarly that they strongly suggest an innate predisposition towards classification. For example, every language contains primary and secondary plant and animal names, *e.g.*, there are apples, and there are granny smiths. This extends to man-made things, *e.g.*, there are knives, and there are hunting knives.

Finding: The classification principle must be supported.

Impact: The generalization relation between Classifiers is used to indicate subcategories of categories. Furthermore, analysis of a compound names can be used to find subcategories, *e.g.*, the name ‘motor vehicle’ indicates that it is a subclass of ‘vehicle’. The guideline ‘Criterion for generalizations’ helps to decide if a generalization is useful in the model. In the example, if there are also non-motorized vehicles (in the targeted domain), and they can participate in different activities or they have different attributes, then a generalization and a class of non-motorized vehicles are useful. If there are non-motorized vehicles, but you do the same with them as with the motor vehicles, then just the class vehicle suffices. (See also the naming guidelines mentioned in *Reflection ‘Involved experts decide about model element names, not the modeler’* (cf. page 52).)

A.7.11 Attributes and steps support indexicals

Bookmark: In the lecture on ‘Philosophy of Language’ [49], John Searle discusses indexical expressions in speech acts. An indexical is an expression whose content varies from one context of use to another. The standard list of indexicals includes pronouns such as ‘I’, ‘you’, ‘he’, ‘she’, ‘it’, ‘this’, ‘that’, plus adverbs such as ‘now’, ‘then’, ‘today’, ‘yesterday’, ‘here’, and ‘actually’. The context determines where they point to exactly.

Finding: The method should support modeling indexicals.

Impact: The step ‘Classify candidates’ has a guideline ‘Definite articles and indexicals indicate an (activity) attribute’. The step ‘Specify Function lifecycle’ has a guideline ‘Check for temporal words in the input text’.

Indexicals appear as Attributes in the specification of Step participants (in an Object, Action, or Function lifecycle). Namely, Attributes can be used anywhere in the scope of it Attribute container. For example, when ordering books online, the shopping cart can be seen as an indexical. It can be referred to in the steps of the ordering process and in the constraints of the ordering process.

Indexicals that express a temporal relation appear as relations between steps in a lifecycle, *e.g.*, select a book and then pay, or in explicit constraints between steps, *e.g.*, paying must be done within 15 minutes after selecting a book.

A.7.12 Support word definitions and word usage

Bookmark: In “From Bacteria to Bach and Back: The Evolution of Minds” [17], Daniel C. Dennett discusses the notion of words and tokens of a word, *i.e.*, the word with the meaning it stands for, and the use of the word in a sentence. The word ‘word’ has four tokens in the previous sentence, and two in this one.

Finding: The method must support this notion too.

Impact: The notion is present at many places, *e.g.*, 1) an Attribute is a token of the type of the Attribute, 2) the use of an Attribute in an Operation call in an Activity view, is a token of the Attribute, 3) a Function step in a Function lifecycle, which is a reference to an Activity, is a token of that Activity. The structure pattern and its derivatives manifest the notion. Any *Reference* in a *Structure* is a token of the *Referred item*.

Besides the notion being present in a model, there is also the instantiation of the model. For example, the occurrence of a domain class instance, aka domain object, can be seen as a token of the domain class.

A.8 More Cognitive Aspects and their Derived Modeling Concepts

A.8.1 Support possible connections between ideas

Bookmark Pinker 10: In “The Sense of Style” [45], Steven Pinker refers to the 1748 book on human understanding of philosopher David Hume: ‘There appear to be only three principles of connections between ideas: similarity, contiguity in time or place, and cause or effect.’ Those connections are expressed as relations between sentences or partial sentences.

1. Similarity: a) similarity: too, similarly, also. b) contrast: but, however, c) exemplification and generalization: either one first, d) exception: generalization first or exception first.
2. Contiguity: a) sequence in time: before, after, b) sequence in place: before, after.
3. Cause effect: a) result: cause first, b) explanation: effect then cause c) violated explanation: preventer effect, d) failed prevention: effect preventer.
4. Pinker observes that one other major coherence relation doesn’t easily fit into Hume’s trichotomy: Attribution, *i.e.*, so-and-so believes such and such. Typical connectives: according to, stated that.

Finding: It seems logical that these principles for connections are supported by the method. We think that the concept of idea from Hume corresponds to model fragment (or model element), because those express some unit of meaning just like idea does.

Impact:

1. Regarding Similarity: the cognitive aspect Analogy reflects the specification of

Appendix A. Cognition-based Reflection Snippets

similarity. Stating that something belongs to a category is also an expression of similarity. Regarding Similarity:

- a) It is possible to create model fragments that are similar to other model fragments, as described in *Reflection 'Support the specification of analogies'* (cf. page 92) on analogy making. What the semantics would be of saying that two model fragments are similar is not clear. However, it could be useful to model, e.g., to see if properties of one model element also hold for another model element. Example: a car is similar to a horse. You can carry stuff with a horse. Can you also carry stuff with a car? Supporting the specification of similarity, i.e., analogy, is future work.
 - b) It is possible to specify contrast connections via guards in structures. For example, 'they choose the shortest way to work, but not on Saturdays' can be represented with a guard on a function step where the route to work is chosen.
 - c) Exemplification and generalization occur during the model discovery stage, i.e., during grammatical analysis, and during model engineering. Also when a model is executed, in order to test it, examples are instantiated from the model.
 - d) It is possible to specify exceptions via constraints.
2. Regarding Contiguity: The cognitive aspect Event has an order relation to Event, which reflects the sequence in time. Contiguity of place is not supported at the moment. It is future work, as suggested in *Reflection 'Support specification of location, force, agency, and causation'* (cf. page 85). Regarding Contiguity:
- a) Sequences in time can be specified via the lifecycle viewpoints. It is also possible to define constraints on the time between two events, i.e., between steps in a lifecycle.
 - b) It makes sense to have modeling concepts specifically for location related aspects, like positioning and movement. This is not supported yet. How to support it is future work.
3. Regarding Cause-effect: An Event may cause another Event. An Agent may perform an Event, which is also a kind of causation. The specification of function lifecycles is specifying what happens when. Via the behavior modality of function steps, the observation and generation of events can be specified, which is also a kind of cause-effect relation.

A.8 More Cognitive Aspects and their Derived Modeling Concepts

- a) The result of an activity is defined in its internal specification. For operations, this is done via a formula. For Domain activities, this is done via its postcondition or its activity view. For Functions, this done via the function lifecycle.
 - b) There is currently no way to specify the deduction of a cause of a result. But it is possible to first specify a postcondition of an activity, and then reason how that postcondition can be guaranteed through steps in the internal specification of that activity.
 - c,d) These are handled the same as a) and b), because the effect is then a negation of a result specification.
4. Regarding Attribution: The cognitive aspect *Property* can be used to attribute one concept to another. Moreover, the notion of 'according to' is also present between a model and its instances. Namely, the instances are in accordance with the model. For example, an attribute *Person.name* of type *Name* states that the attribute has the properties of the class *Name*. Or, the use of an operation in an activity means that the activity works in accordance with how that operation works. The notion of 'believes' does not make sense for specifications.

A.8.2 Support the specification of hierarchy between concepts

Bookmark: Hofstadter and Sander observe in "Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking" [26] that concepts are hierarchical. We are building concepts from other concepts throughout our whole life. But it does not lead to a hierarchy of concepts in our mind. It is not determined that a newer concept comprises the older concept. The older concept is also changed by creating a new concept with it.

Finding: We conclude that hierarchy should be seen as something that can be expressed in a specification.

Impact: The cognitive aspect *Property* reflects hierarchy. It is possible to define new concepts from other concepts via several relation types, such as behavior life dependency, generalization, attribute, involvement. The main mechanism in the metamodel is the structure pattern and its derivatives (see Section 6.1 in the paper).

A.8.3 Support making abstractions

Bookmark Hofstadter 2: In “Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking” [26] Hofstadter and Sander observe that we (people) are constantly abstracting. ‘This is not stupidity, but intelligence.’

Finding: Support making abstractions. A link to the ‘real’ world helps people to create and use abstract knowledge. In other words, abstractions must still be recognizable by people.

Impact: To make abstractions, MuDForM offers the concept of *Generalizations* between *Classifiers*, which is based on the cognitive aspect *Property*. Using types, *i.e.*, *Classifiers*, is itself also a mechanism to create abstractions. Namely, the metamodel element *Classifier*, which is based on the cognitive aspect *Category*, is an abstraction of a set of instances. For example, the classifier *Apple* can be seen as an abstraction of one or more specific apples. Making domain models is making abstractions.

A.8.4 Support the specification of analogies

Bookmark Hofstadter 3: Hofstadter and Sander focus in “Surfaces and Essences, Analogy as the Fuel and Fire of Thinking” [26] on analogy making being in the core of our mental processes. At the end of the book, Hofstadter and Sander state that category making and analogy making are really the same mental process. You cannot do one without doing the other.

Finding: Analogy making should be possible. But, we need to decide if we should distinct categories and analogies. And, if so, how?

Impact: In the cognitive aspects model (see Section 5 of *the paper*), we have kept the difference between *Analogy* and *Category*, because they are expressed in different ways. An analogy is expressed as a relation between two things. A *Category* is expressed as an abstraction of a set of things. Not all experiences, *i.e.*, analogy makings, are leading to a specified category. Moreover, when designing a system, one can define *categories* of things that should be created without those things being experienced yet. So, an *Analogy* does not necessarily lead to an explicit *Category*. Vice versa, a thing can be said to belong to a *Category* without making an *Analogy* to one or more other things in that *Category*.

Category and *Analogy* are both a subclass of *Concept*. So, it is possible to state

that a specific analogy and category are the same thing. How to support analogy making with specific modeling concepts requires more investigation and is future work.

A.8.5 Any model fragment can be seen as a pattern

Bookmark: Michael Shermer talks in “The Believing Brain” [50] about the concept of patternicity. Seeing patterns has evolved as a mechanism for survival and reproduction, especially to relate cause and effect. The fact that people see patterns even when they are not there is not necessarily harmful to them.

Finding: It should be possible to specify patterns. It should be possible to apply patterns in a specification. Any piece of model should be usable as a pattern and, as such, serve as the foundation for an analogy in the way Hofstadter and Sander (see *Bookmark Hofstadter 3 (cf. page 92)*) mean it. A model can be seen as a directed acyclic graph, without any external semantics, *i.e.*, a model does not have semantics because the names of model elements have meaning; it has semantics because the model is expressed completely in terms of the metamodel.

Impact: It is possible to take a piece of model, and rename the parts. This is how each model fragment can be used as a pattern. It is not directly supported with specific modeling concepts for defining patterns.

The metamodel currently does not provide an explicit pattern mechanism. Treating a model fragment as a pattern can simply be done by copying the model fragment and replacing the names by the desired names.

The method definition can be extended with modeling use cases or modeling functions. One of those use cases can be the making of an analogy. To realize this, the metamodel should be augmented with modeling activities. Activities are now only modeled for the grammatical analysis phase. If also the metamodel is expressed in terms of activities, then applying a pattern could be seen as a (modeling) function with a flow that contains steps typed by those activities. Applying a pattern is basically copying a set of related model elements, *i.e.*, selecting a model fragment, then renaming each of them or replacing them with an existing model element, and then integrating the created model fragment into the target model. The realization of this use case is future work.

A.8.6 Distinguish performative from constative speech acts

Bookmark: In the lectures on “Philosophy of Language” [49], John Searle writes about the difference between performative speech acts and constative speech acts. A performative speech act is performing an action by saying something, *e.g.*, ‘waiter, get me a beer please’ is the act of ordering a beer. The constative speech act would be ‘the waiter is getting me a beer’. Another aspect is that a performative one is always true, the constative one can be false. Speech acts can also be both, *e.g.*, when the waiter says ‘I promise that I will get you a beer’. The promise part is performative, but the actually getting part is constative.

Finding: Information (software) systems, and administrative domains in general, are all about automating performative speech acts, *e.g.*, ordering a beer via an app on your phone. It can be useful to express the difference between performative and constative speech acts in a model.

Impact: In function flows, you can specify the behavior modality of a function step; you can say 1) that you execute the step, *i.e.*, the actor that is executing the function will also execute the function step 2) that you want the step to be executed, *i.e.*, an event is sent to the function execution environment to execute the step or 3) that you observe the step being executed (and react to it), *i.e.*, an event is received from the function execution environment that the step is executed. A software system can execute a function step if the action that defines it is a performative act. Constative speech acts can only be controlled by a software system, *e.g.*, via a call to the context to let some actor (person or machine) perform the act, or observed by a software system, *e.g.*, via a physical sensor or when an end user indicates that the action happened.

It could be useful to have a distinction between physical and conceptual activities in the domain model. Namely, it is in the nature of the activity and not in the context in which the activity is used. In the example of ordering a book, the software execution is the implementation of the ordering of a book by a person. In case of a physical action, like delivering a book, the software execution may control the delivery, but it does not do the delivery. Investigating the support for and benefits from different types of speech acts –there are more types than discussed here– is future work.

B Vision: Software Development is a Human Task

Software development can be seen as the integration of knowledge and decisions from multiple people that are responsible for different aspects. Software languages are mostly based on computer-based primitives, which was logical when computers were expensive in comparison to developing costs. Today's software costs are dominated by the cost of development personnel. In other words, people are more important for the success of a development activity than computers. A development method should reflect this. Our vision is that software development is intrinsically a cooperative human task, which should be supported by a method that is based on (human) cognitive concepts, instead of computer-based concepts.

The foundation for the vision is based on Chapter 2 of the book *DYA* [Software [16]]. The writing of that chapter led to the need to investigate what specification method could realize the vision. It is elaborated in our position report [10].

The vision is formed by four pillars, which each address an important issue in today's software development practice. These issues frame the research goal that we want to address.

A development method should enable people to communicate and reason in their own domain language. Software development has started as a specialism, in which software engineers performed every development task, and needed to have all the required knowledge to do so. Since then, software systems have become larger and the number of stakeholders and aspects to deal with during their development has increased. Software development involves people in many areas of expertise.

Appendix B. Vision: Software Development is a Human Task

These people each speak their own “language” with their idiom, and sometimes with their own grammar and syntax. Nevertheless, the practice is that we still use (development) languages that are an aggregation of computer-based primitives. The research problem that we want to address is **how to support all people involved in a development project with their own language?**

A development method should help to guard the consistency of all specifications in the development process. Tools and methods, each with their own notations and artifacts, are already available and used for some domains in the development process, *e.g.*, requirement management, project management, modeling, or code checking. These tools and methods are mostly not integrated in a coherent chain, despite their overlap in concepts and their interdependencies. For example, a requirements engineer uses a requirement management tool and a tester uses a test tool. Although a test tool might allow you to refer to requirements, there is typically no support to guard the consistency between the requirements specification and the (related) test specifications. Integral specification consistency is often not managed explicitly, let alone guaranteed. The research problem that we want to address is **how to ensure the consistency across all specifications in a system’s development?**

Development methods should support the explicit specification of any quality. In the early days of software development, a computer with software offered functionality in a way that was not possible before. Nowadays, functionality of software is only unique for a short time, and is quickly offered by multiple suppliers. The business success factor of software has shifted from functionality to system qualities like ease of use, availability, security, and sustainability, and to development qualities like time-to-market, development cost, and project predictability. In spite of that, development methods and tools are still focused on delivering software functionality instead of guaranteeing quality. Architecture approaches related to quality, like ATAM [29] and architectural tactics [5], systematize the process, but not the specification of the involved requirements, designs, and their relations. Moreover, the desired quality is often not specified at all. The effect is that personal beliefs and experience of developers determine the quality of developed software. When a development team consists of people with different backgrounds, this results in inconsistent quality throughout a system and its development. This situation clearly contradicts the just stated business importance of quality. Any system property, including quality, cannot be proven, guaranteed, or engineered consistently, when it is not specified. Hence, the research problem that we want to address is **how to support the specification of all required qualities and their relations?**

Development methods should support the reuse of any decision made in a system's lifetime: from idea to requirement, design, test, and system evolution. A software system is the result of a series of development decisions. Making good decisions costs significant time and money. One must learn the involved domains and consider trade-offs between all kinds of concerns. The reuse of a good decision in another context increases the return on investment in that decision. To make a decision reusable, it should at least be specified. Most reuses of decisions go via artifacts that capture the result of a set of decisions, *e.g.*, a piece of source code. Those artifacts can be part of the working system like a GUI library, a DBMS, or a rule engine, or can be part of any intermediate product during development, like a standard set of security requirements, process models, or design patterns. Also reusable transformations, *e.g.*, via a code generator, can be artifacts that capture development decisions. This kind of decision reuse is common practice in today's software development. However, it is often unclear which decisions exactly are reused, and whether they should have been reused at all. The result can be that expensive development knowledge is wasted, because the decisions are not reusable. The reuse of decision results starts with their specification. The research problem that we want to address is **how to support the specification of knowledge and decisions such that they are reusable (in another context)?**

C Research Goal

Some of today's techniques solve part of the stated research problems, *e.g.*, like natural language processing, domain modeling, domain-specific languages, model driven development, method engineering, design patterns, product line architectures, and IDEs. Furthermore, many formalisms, *e.g.*, set theory, calculus, and process algebra, may be used to enable automated reuse of specified decisions. But these techniques and formalisms are not integrated, and not applied to every aspect of a system's lifecycle.

To bring software development close to the thinking and communication of all stakeholders, we want to connect it to cognitive sciences, linguistics, and philosophy. Our research will realistically not be able to cover all potentially relevant knowledge in these fields. We mostly want to break ground for approaching software engineering as a process of knowledge capturing, more than a process of realizing executable software functionality. We understand that functionality is relevant. But we advocate that it should not be the foundation and focus of a development approach. A method and language based on cognitive concepts instead of machine primitives, and that is independent of any domain, should be the foundation for a system's lifecycle that does not suffer from the issues described in the previous section. This leads to our main research question (RQ):

What specification method enables all people involved in system development to unambiguously specify knowledge and decisions in a way that is close to how they think and communicate?

D Method Objectives

Based on the vision, and our experience with domain modeling, architecture, and model driven development, we have defined a set of objectives for our method – called MuDForM (Multi-Domain Formalization Method). They are not intended as a complete set of method requirements, but they form the rationale for the method definition, and for the method engineering approach. They are also the yardstick for evaluating existing specification techniques as potential content for the definition of MuDForM. The objectives are:

- O1 In any software development process, there are people that have concerns about different aspects. People use terminology from the domain that they are knowledgeable about, when they express their knowledge and decisions. A development method should support the **distinction of multiple domains** in one specification, to deal with the multitude of aspects in a development process. Moreover, a specification method should offer multiple mechanisms, *e.g.*, composition, consistency rules, transformation, or weaving, to integrate domain specifications, and domain-based specifications.
- O2 There is no limitation to what kind of aspects can be relevant in software development. A specification method should therefore be **independent of any domain** or system, and a method user (modeler) should not need any prior knowledge about the domain or system that is being specified. In practice, domain modeling is mostly used for the application domains of targeted systems, or for the design aspects of software. We think domain modeling should also be applicable to quality domains, such as reliability, security, usability, or

Appendix D. Method Objectives

functional safety, like in the case study of a previous publication [14].

- O3 Knowledge about particular aspects can be seen independently of any specific (software) system, and is potentially usable in more than one system. A specification method should reflect this and produce **self-contained specifications** that are independent of their application in a specific system. To use specifications in different contexts, *i.e.*, to build other specifications, they should be composable, interpretable, and translatable.
- O4 Specifications can be made to analyze what is known about a domain, *i.e.*, specify what can happen and what can exist, and to design what should be true for a domain, *i.e.*, specify what shall happen and what shall exist. Therefore, a specification method should support the **distinction between descriptive specifications and prescriptive specifications**, and their relations.
- O5 Most domains and systems are not only about entities with a state, but also about change. A method should therefore support both the **specification of state** at a certain moment, and the **specification of change** of state over time. In other words, specifications should address things that exist, things that happen, and how those things are related. This perspective is similar to the notion of structural (static) properties and behavioral (dynamic) properties in UML [40].
- O6 Almost all people, including domain experts, use natural language to convey their knowledge and decisions. It is used in many documents in any software development process. A specification method should support the **transformation of** knowledge stated in **natural language** into specifications in an unambiguous language. Preferably, such specifications should themselves be translatable into natural language. The purpose of this support is to minimize loss of semantics and better mutual understanding in the communication between modelers and domain experts. The use of natural language as entry point for modeling is a stepping stone for the realization of the MuDForM vision to have method concepts that are close to human cognition. Natural language is a starting point, but probably does not cover all relevant cognitive concepts, because it evolved for communication and not specifically for thinking.
- O7 A specification **method should be engineered**, which means it should support specification consistency and completeness, elicitation of knowledge, and traceability of decisions, and it should have a comprehensive definition. According to Kronlöf [31] a method definition should contain the following ingredients:

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- An underlying model, *e.g.*, metamodel, core model, or abstract syntax, which defines the modeling concepts, *i.e.*, the elements of the modeling language, and the semantics of a specification.
 - An explicit notation, possibly used in different viewpoints. All the viewpoints of the method should be defined in terms of the concepts of the underlying model.
 - Explicit method steps that guide the modeler, from eliciting knowledge from documents and experts, to making a consistent and complete model.
 - Guidance for taking steps and making specification decisions.

O8 The purpose of a specification is mostly to (partially) realize (part of) a system. Hence, the transition from a set of created (domain-oriented) specifications into a working system should be feasible. In other words, there should be a **clear relation between specification method and architecture**.

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